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Characterization of Optical Fiber Performance:
Automated FRD/SG Measurement and
Modal Noise Investigation at a high-resolution Spectrograph

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Charakterisierung der Qualität von optischen Fasern: Automatisierte FRD/SG-Messung und Untersuchung von Modal Noise mit einem hochauflösenden Spektrographen

Die Ziele dieser Arbeit sind die Entwicklung eines automatisierten Systems zur Untersuchung von optischen Fasern sowie die Vertiefung des Verständnisses der bei Fasern auftretenden Effekte. Es wurden Focal Ratio Degradation (FRD), Scrambling Gain (SG) und Modal Noise (MN) für eine Auswahl von Fasern mit unterschiedlichen Kerngeometrien und -größen untersucht. Die Arbeit ist in zwei Teile geteilt:

Der erste Teil handelt vom Mess- und Analysesystem, welches zur FRD und SG Messung verwendet wird. Es werden die Details des Aufbaus und dessen Hardware-Komponente erläutert und es wird auf die Schritte zur Datenanalyse eingegangen. Zusätzlich wird die Vorbereitung der Fasern, also das Polieren und Konfektionieren, gezeigt. Es wird außerdem ein Beispiel eines automatisch generierten Berichts präsentiert, welcher zum Urteilen über die Qualität einer Faser dient. Beispielhafte FRD und SG Ergebnissen einer breiten Auswahl von Fasern werden vorgestellt.

Der zweite Teil befasst sich mit der detaillierten Analyse von Modal Noise Daten, die mithilfe des Waltz Spektrographen und verschiedener Testfasern aufgenommen wurden. Der Fokus dieser Untersuchung liegt auf den Noise-Unterschieden zwischen den verwendeten Multi-, Few- und Single-Mode Fasern. Um sowohl die Frequenzabhängigkeit als auch die alleinige Magnitude von MN zu beurteilen, werden einfache statistische Untersuchungen sowie Fourier-Analysen verwendet. Ergebnisse zeigen die beste MN Eigenschaften bei Single-Mode fasern, gefolgt von multi-mode und zuletzt few-mode fasern, welche am schlechtesten abgeschlossen haben.

Characterization of Optical Fiber Performance: Automated FRD/SG Measurement and Modal Noise Investigation at a high-resolution Spectrograph

The objectives of this thesis are the development of an automated system that measures the optical properties of fibers and to gain a deeper understanding of the occurring effects. Focal Ratio Degradation (FRD), Scrambling Gain (SG) and Modal Noise (MN) are measured and investigated for an assortment of fibers with differing core shapes and sizes. The thesis is split in two parts:

The first part covers the measurement and analysis system, that is used to measure FRD and SG. Details about the setup, its hardware components and the control software are explained, while also covering the steps that are taken to analyze the data. Furthermore the steps taken to polish and assemble fibers are shown, as well as an example of an automated report, that was generated to judge the performance of a fiber. Exemplary Focal Ratio Degradation and Scrambling Gain data of a vast set of optical fibers is presented.

The second part involves a detailed analysis of MN data collected using the Waltz spectrograph and multiple test fibers. The focus of the investigation is on differences with respect to qualitative changes in the core sizes of the included multi-, few-, and single-mode fibers. The analysis employs simple statistical and Fourier analyses to evaluate frequency dependence and overall magnitude of the noise. Results show, that few-mode fibers experience the worst MN, while large core multi-mode fibers perform much better, and single-mode fibers are least affected.

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1 Introduction

Optical fibers are widely used in modern astronomy. Most present-day spectrographs are fiber-fed, meaning the light from the telescope is carried to the instrument via optical fibers in contrast to a slit-fed design. This allows for more flexibility in operating the telescope and a detachment of telescope and instrument. The environment of the instrument then can be highly controlled, enabling e.g. improved temperature and pressure control as well as keeping it mechanically stable, completely avoiding gravitational flexure and vibration. Beneficial is also a fiber's property to scramble the carried light, which reduces guiding and seeing variations of the illumination of the spectrograph. All this leads to an improvement of the spectrograph's precision.

Spectroscopy finds use in various fields, like radial velocity (RV) measurement for exoplanet detection, stellar atmospheres, chemical composition studies, cosmological redshift, and more. The interest and requirements for these instruments grow steadily, and so do the requirements for the operating fibers.

This thesis aims to deepen the understanding of fiber effects, their connection to physical properties and their potential mitigation. Additionally I present a way of automating the measurement of some of these effects.

The first part of the thesis focuses on measuring fiber effects, specifically Focal Ratio Degradation (FRD) and Scrambling Gain (SG). Creating a large database containing a wide variety of fibers helps to establish a connection between FRD or SG, and the physical attributes of fibers, such as their core size, shape, and length. This part mostly focuses on the measurement procedure to define the fiber properties and the specific way automation of such measurements in the lab was handled. Other research of fiber properties has mostly covered small numbers of fibers, measured in the same setup (See e.g.: Y. Yan et al. 2025; Oliva et al. 2019; Jesulino Bispo Dos Santos et al. 2014; Lee et al. 2024). This makes comparisons between researchers difficult. Thereby a larger database of fibers with a wide range of physical properties and good repeatability by automation, would give new and more clear insights to fiber behavior.

The second part of the thesis aims to closely examine modal noise (MN) in-situ at the Waltz spectrograph to see how exactly MN affects spectra in a high-resolution spectrograph. Different types of measurements and methods of analysis are covered, in order to gain insight of how modal noise affects spectra and how dependent it is on fiber properties. The measurements were carried out with the Waltz spectrograph at the Landessternwarte (LSW). The Waltz-telescope utilizes a fiber-fed échelle spectrograph with a resolution of $R \approx 65000$ and an approximate wavelength coverage of $450 - 750nm$. Five different fibers were used for testing: Two in the few mode range, one single-mode and two multimode fibers. The different fibers were chosen as such to represent different ranges of carried numbers of modes.

1.1 Motivation

Instruments like HARPS, ESPRESSO or upcoming ones like MARVEL, ANDES or 2ES are few examples of instruments utilizing optical fibers. Some of which push for 0.1 m/s precision in radial velocity measurements. For high-precision spectrographs like that, an advanced understanding of how optical fibers influence the measurements is essential.

Focal Ratio Degradation is a property of fibers in which the output light beam has a wider cone angle than the input beam. The more pronounced this effect is, the more challenging it is to design instruments around it. With wider beams, each component needs to be designed larger or significant loss of light must be expected. FRD is an established obstacle in spectrograph design (See e.g. Raskin et al. 2011) and insuring minimal throughput loss is vital for the spectrographs performance.

Scrambling Gain on the other hand is an advantageous property of fibers. Fibers tend to scramble the spatial information of the carried light. This in turn removes or mitigates variabilities produced by guiding and seeing in the input of the spectrograph. Trifonov et al. (2020) show how better SG abilities improve the instrument's performance. Characterizing SG capabilities thoroughly therefore directly influences a spectrographs potential.

Modal noise is a disadvantageous optical effect of multimode fibers. The interference between propagation modes that carry the light through a fiber results in a speckle pattern at its output. These patterns introduce a high-frequency, wavelength dependent noise to the spectrum that is not static between exposures. Several high-precision spectrographs determine MN as a significant noise contributor (E.g. Blackman et al. 2020; Donati et al. 2020; H. R. Jones et al. 2021). Although there are established mitigation strategies (See Oliva et al. 2019) to limit the MN influence, as e.g. agitation, a better understanding of the effect or finding other ways of mitigation can lead to new limits for spectrograph precision.

The instrumentation group at the LSW is involved in several projects related to fiber-fed instruments: 2ES, MARVEL, and ANDES-K. Contributions include the production of fiber links for four telescopes and the calibration unit for MARVEL, as well as for one telescope, one calibration unit, and a solar telescope for 2ES. For each involved fiber there are set thresholds for their expected properties, both for SG and FRD. Ensuring that these thresholds are met before and after installation is crucial, because they directly impact the instrument's precision. A reliable, repeatable, and (with the number of fibers involved) quick way of measuring and judging the fibers is essential, especially with the set goal of 10 cm/s precision for 2ES. In case of ANDES-K, we investigated modal noise, to find solutions to minimize or mitigate its influence on the spectrum. Since the instrument works in the near-infrared, thermal background radiation is a limiting factor for the fiber size. Small core fibers are planned to be employed to keep out as much thermal radiation as possible. Few-mode fibers like that are much more prone to higher modal noise, hence the importance to first see how severe the MN would be and

potentially find alternatives. The Max Planck Institute of Astrophysics in Heidelberg provided us with two few-mode fibers to test under realistic conditions at the Waltz spectrograph. The fibers were chosen to reflect the number of modes in the visual as the planned fibers would have in the K-band for ANDES. We tested the two fibers and added one single-mode and two other multi-mode fibers for reference. This provides data to judge the suitability of the fibers for the ANDES K-band spectrograph.

Beyond these demands, both an automated measuring system and a closer look at MN are useful in the bigger picture. There is no standardized SG or FRD measurement procedure across institutes. Differences in illumination or calibration conditions, as well as other discrepancies, lead to a high degree of scatter in published data, making cross-comparisons between studies nearly impossible. Reproducibility is hard to ensure without an automated setup. The scarcity of fiber data, and thus the inability to create larger datasets, can result in missed correlations between the physical properties of fibers and SG or FRD. While there are largely accepted correlations, e.g. core shape with SG, there might be more intricate connections only unveiled by larger amounts of data across more different fibers and fiber types. This effort may not have not been proven fruitful in the course of my thesis, but the development of an easy to use, automated, GUI controlled fiber measurement system allows our dataset to grow with each newly measured fiber. Over time, this makes the dataset more valuable. Older measurements remain valid, and the whole dataset can be compared at any point to identify trends. Even aging trends could become visible, when remeasuring the fibers.

The modal noise measurements also provide a basis for further research in that direction. By establishing how modal noise looks in its raw form and what characteristics it follows, we can learn more about the intrinsic mechanism by which it is governed. Many factors MN depends on are still poorly constrained. Learning about the exact way of its formation, could allow for its prediction and subsequent reduction. Dependence on core size could establish higher awareness of the disadvantages of few-mode fibers, allowing for more informed spectrograph designs. Raw data reveals spatial frequencies, temporal variability and intensity. This thesis provides a baseline for deeper inquiries on the dependence of Modal Noise on several factors.

1.2 Scope and Objectives

As mentioned before the main objective of this thesis is to develop a system for measuring fibers and gain a deeper look into their optical effects. The first part of the thesis followed the goal to accumulate as much SG and FRD fiber data as possible. This of course implies multiple sub objectives, as measuring all the properties of numerous fibers is a lengthy endeavor. That is why, a lot of my time has gone towards automating the fiber measurement process as much as possible. In that sense, I developed a custom GUI based system to control the laboratory setup, which is used to measure the fibers. The working principle, theory and practical implementation will be the topic of the first part of this thesis. With this fiber measurement system I have measured about 15 different fibers so far. A few of these were also assembled and polished by

me. Learning the necessary steps to get from a bare fiber to a fully usable one, were also part of my work, and will be briefly explained in the later chapters of this part. The SG and FRD results of the fibers that have been measured so far will also be discussed briefly.

As an interesting example, beyond the fibers that I assembled, there was a $25 \times 40\mu\text{m}$ -core, rectangular fiber with rounded edges, dubbed "Stadium"-fiber and an octagonal $50\mu\text{m}$ -core fiber. These types of fibers will be installed in the 2ES spectrograph (See Julian Stürmer, Buchhave, et al. 2024), and my measurements were used to judge their suitability for the project. The results for the stadium-fiber and an example of an automatically generated fiber-report, can be seen in Appendix B.

The general goal of the second part of the thesis, is to test how modal noise is affected by different factors. We test modal noise (MN) under agitation, change of input coupling and see how the MN pattern changes with time. We examine these factors for different types of fibers to determine how the effects scale with the number of modes in a fiber. A list and the specifications of the used fibers can be seen in Table 1.1. All tested fibers are circular in their core shape, but have varying core size and NA. These remaining parameters determine the number of modes, with which light of a given wavelength is carried.

To obtain a comprehensive picture of how MN exactly affects spectra, we utilize a number of methods to determine MN characteristics. We use statistical noise analysis and Fourier analysis of the spectra to identify spatial and frequency dependencies. Additionally we use time-series to study temporal instabilities. These methods were partly carried out per échelle-order or over the whole extracted and wavelength-solved spectrum.

Fiber Name	Core Diameter [μm]	NA	Type	Resources
C-100	100	0.22	Multimode	
C-18	18	0.22	Multimode	
M64L02	10	0.10	Few-mode	Thorlabs, Inc. 2023a
28E10	8.2	0.14	Few-mode	Thorlabs, Inc. 2023c
	MFD $\approx 9.2\mu\text{m}$ @1310nm			
M460B	<2	0.10 – 0.14	Single-mode	Thorlabs, Inc. 2023b
	MFD $\approx 2.8 - 4.1$ @488nm			

Table 1.1: Names and relevant specifications for used fibers.

2 Theoretical Background

Exoplanet research is one of the major driving areas of spectrograph development. A landmark achievement was the detection of the first planet around a Sun-like star by Mayor and Queloz (1995), using RV spectroscopy. These findings mark the beginning of an ever growing field in astronomy. With the use and discovery of other methods (See Figure 2.2), the number of confirmed exoplanets has been growing faster every year, as seen in Figure 2.1. Today the number of confirmed exoplanets is around 6000¹. The majority of discoveries are owed to the transit method, which had its first exoplanet discovery in 2002 (Konacki et al. 2003). Although the transit method may seem superior based on the number of discoveries, it does not render RV measurements obsolete. The methods complement each other by confirming the existence of planets and gaining more data about e.g. the exoplanets mass. By refining the precision of spectrographs, smaller differences in RV can be measured and smaller planets can be confirmed and discovered. Earth like planets require precision of 10cm/s in RV, which is the goal for current leading edge spectrographs like 2ES (Julian Stürmer, Buchhave, et al. 2024). Some limiting factors of precision that have to be managed are the utilized fibers. Fiber-fed échelle spectrographs make up the major demographic of high-resolution instruments for radial velocity measurements. This is the established standard, since fibers allow for flexible instrument placement and échelle gratings can reach high resolving power in a more constrained space, by exploiting high diffraction orders.

¹NASA Exoplanet Archive

Figure 2.1: Cumulative number of discovered exoplanets by year and method. (Source: Mathieu 2024).

Figure 2.2: Exoplanet detection methods. (Source: European Space Agency (ESA) 2019b).

2.1 Radial Velocity Measurements

Radial velocity measurements are based on the Doppler-effect. Objects moving away from an observer are red-shifted and objects moving towards are blue-shifted. Since a host star and its planet move around a common barycenter, there are small variations of the stellar spectrum due to periodic blue and redshift. Figure 2.3 shows this Doppler spectroscopy in action. By measuring the shift of known spectral lines, the radial velocity can be calculated. This though just gives the velocity in the direction of the line-of-sight at one instance. To gain a more complete understanding of an exoplanets orbit, many measurements are combined to a plot like the one in Figure 2.4. The observed Doppler velocity is defined by

$$K = v_{star} \cdot \sin(i) \quad (2.1)$$

where v_{star} is the real velocity of the parent star and i is the inclination. The inclination cannot be determined by RV measurements alone and must be found e.g. by the transit method if applicable. Assuming vanishing eccentricity to simplify calculations, one can determine the minimum mass of the exoplanet, given the orbital period, as well as the mass of the host star (which can be determined by stellar models in most cases):

$$M_P = v_{star} \sqrt{\frac{r M_{star}}{G}} \quad (2.2)$$

Here M_{star} is the mass of the host star and G is the gravitational constant. r is the distance between the host and the companion:

$$r^3 = \frac{GM_{star}}{4\pi^2} P_{star}^2 \quad (2.3)$$

Calculating the planet's mass without considering the inclination of its orbit would always yield a minimum value. This is because the observed radial velocity is always the minimum of the star's true velocity. The more tilted the orbit is with respect to the line of sight, the more the true velocity is underestimated by the Doppler velocity.

The radial velocity can be derived from the spectrum like so

$$RV = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_0} \cdot c \quad (2.4)$$

where c is the speed of light, λ_0 is the wavelength of the spectral line if the star was fixed, and $\Delta\lambda$ is the spectral shift.

Figure 2.3: Doppler effect for stars moving around the barycenter of their system. Spectral lines are used to measure the precise amount of red- or blue-shift to then calculate the radial velocity at the instance of observation. (Source: European Space Agency (ESA) 2019a).

Figure 2.4: Radial velocities of G1 581, a red dwarf some 20 Ly away, as function of orbital phase. The curve resembles a circular orbit with a period of 5.366 days. (Source: European Southern Observatory (ESO) 2005).

Figure 2.5: **Left:** Diffraction from a blazed grating. (Source: Svdmolen 2014)

Right: Working principle of an échelle spectrograph. (Source: Považay 2007).

2.2 Échelle Spectrograph

An échelle spectrograph uses high diffraction orders to achieve high resolution spectra. Key component is the échelle grating, which is designed for large blaze angles. Figure 2.5 (left) shows the principle of how light interacts with a blazed grating. The blaze angle is set so that the grating is most efficient in the desired orders and wavelength, suppressing lower diffraction orders. The light paths of the high diffraction orders are spaced close together, leading to overlap regions. In an échelle spectrograph the diffraction orders are separated by a secondary dispersive element, perpendicular to the échelle grating. As shown in Figure 2.5 (right), this result in multiple stacked sub-spectra enveloping the whole desired spectrum.

The free spectral range (FSR) defines the range of wavelength of the sub-spectra which are not overlapping with other diffraction orders:

$$\Delta\lambda = \frac{\lambda}{m} \quad (2.5)$$

where λ is the wavelength and m the diffraction order. The blaze wavelength is given by:

$$\lambda_{blaze} = \frac{2d \sin(\theta_B)}{m} \quad (2.6)$$

with d the line spacing, θ_B the blaze angle and m again the diffraction order.

The resulting number of sub-spectra or orders to display the whole spectrum can be around 50, as for the Waltz spectrograph. An example image of the Waltz échelle spectrum is shown in Figure 8.2.

2.3 Optical Properties of Fibers

Optical fibers are widely used in astronomy to carry light from telescopes to instruments. Since these instruments are designed to be highly accurate, they are placed in highly controlled environments some distance from the actual telescope. Considering that optical fibers can carry light over long distances, while remaining flexible, they are a perfect candidate for this use case. Optical fibers are typically made up of three layers: core, cladding, and coating. The light is injected into the core of the fiber, where it gets constantly reflected at the boundary between core and cladding. The difference of the refractive indices between the materials used for core and cladding define the numerical aperture (NA) and the maximum angle at which light is still reflected.

$$NA = \sqrt{n_{core}^2 - n_{clad}^2} \quad (2.7)$$

$$n \cdot \sin(\theta_{max}) = NA \quad (2.8)$$

where n_{core} is the refractive index of the fiber core, n_{clad} that of the cladding and n that of the medium surrounding the fiber.

Typical defining parameters of any fiber are: Core size, Core shape and NA.

2.3.1 Fiber Modes

The propagation of light in dielectric waveguides such as optical fibers are defined by the Maxwell equations. We will not go in depth towards that matter, as its relevance is limited, and there are plenty of works available that cover it in a more curated manner than what would be possible here (see e.g. Snyder, Love, et al. 1983). Relevant for the following discussion is that when light is injected into a fiber, a number of modes are excited, depending on wavelength, NA and core diameter of the fiber.

The V-number is a parameter used to characterize some modal properties of a fiber:

$$V = \frac{\pi \cdot d \cdot NA}{\lambda} \quad (2.9)$$

With: d the fiber diameter, NA the numerical aperture, and λ the wavelength.

Single mode behavior is achieved for: $V \lesssim 2.405$. For multimode fibers the number of supported modes can be approximated as:

$$M \approx \frac{V^2}{2} \quad (2.10)$$

In the weakly guided approximation² the linearly polarized (LP) modes can be defined, see Figure 2.6.

These propagation modes each have their own set of properties: Effective refractive index, group velocity, effective mode area, and more. The properties then influence attributes such as bend loss or mode dependent phase change. That means that light of the same wavelength, traveling via different modes, experience a phase shift at the far-end of the fiber. This leads to a speckle pattern at the output fiber face, examples of which can be seen in Figure 2.7.

²See Gloge 1971, for details.

Figure 2.6: Linearly polarized modes governing light propagation in the weakly guided approximation. Source: RP Photonics Encyclopedia (Paschotta 2025).

Figure 2.7: Speckle patterns for different fiber diameters at 520nm. Fiber core diameters are, from left to right: $16\mu\text{m}$, $35\mu\text{m}$, $105\mu\text{m}$, $160\mu\text{m}$. Image reproduced from: A. Wang et al. 2024.

2.3.2 Focal Ratio Degradation

Focal Ratio Degradation describes the effect of a changing focal ratio, or cone angle, of the in- and output beam of a fiber. While the perfect fiber would preserve the focal ratio, more realistic cases show that the output F-ratio is faster, resulting in a wider beam. The F-ratio is defined by

$$f/\# = \frac{1}{2 * \tan(\theta_0)} \quad (2.11)$$

where θ_0 is the cone angle of the beam. In instrumentation this can result in the necessity of larger optics at the output side of such fibers, which then results in more challenging and more costly designs. If FRD is not accounted for, it results in throughput losses, since elements of the instrument clip the widened parts of the beam. The factors contributing to FRD are typically mechanical stress, bending, quality of the fiber end-face and material impurities (Haynes et al. 2011). FRD is also significantly worsened, when the optical axis of the input beam and the one of the fiber are misaligned. The fiber has to be carefully aligned with the beam to avoid producing artificially worse FRD. Bending can occur as micro-bending e.g. when gluing the fiber into a ferrule and the glue shrinks. That is why low-shrinkage epoxies like EPO-TEK 301-2 usually find application in the gluing process (Oliveira, L. De Oliveira, and J. Dos Santos 2005).

2.3.3 Scrambling Gain

While FRD is an unwanted effect, Scrambling Gain affects the light in a more useful manner. It describes the fiber's ability to loose the spatial information of the input beam. Meaning, as shown in Figure 2.8), if for instance light in the form of a small spot is projected on the fiber end, given a large enough SG value, the output end will be evenly illuminated. We use SG as defined by

$$SG = \frac{d_i/D_i}{d_o/D_o} \quad (2.12)$$

where d is the displacement of the center-of-mass (COM) of the flux from the center of the fiber and D the core diameter of the fiber, for input and output respectively. For most fibers with a circular core, the output fiber face will typically display an illuminated circle (see Figure 2.8), instead of an evenly illuminated surface. This or the appearance of any uneven structure in the fiber output is a sign of bad scrambling.

When there is good scrambling however, the effect is beneficial for measuring spectra. The physical position of the star on the input fiber-end will be scrambled and therefore have less influence on the fiber's output and the spectrum. This eliminates or mitigates the noise resulting from positional inconsistencies at the fiber input, as induced by guiding or seeing variations.

Figure 2.8: Near-field fiber face images of an example measurement. The top-row displays input and output of a $89\mu\text{m}$ octagonal-core fiber, respectively. Here the output illumination is evenly distributed. The bottom-row displays input and output of a $100\mu\text{m}$ circular-core fiber, where the output illumination shows a clear circular pattern.

2.3.4 Modal Noise

Modal noise is an almost inevitable, intrinsic source of noise in any fiber-fed spectrograph. It arises due to the interference of light of different modes that are carried in a fiber. When exiting the fiber, light combines from different modes, which have different relative phases. This leads to interference and in turn creates a speckle pattern.

In a fiber-fed spectrograph the fiber output is directly used as spectrograph input. Therefore spatial instabilities, as in the case of a speckle pattern, directly translate to spatial instabilities of the intensity distribution at each spectrograph component. Since there is always some cut-off or loss in light due to spatial restrictions of some components and since the speckle pattern is dependent on wavelength, there are wavelength sensitive differences in the loss. These differences are due to the change of the speckle pattern and whether or not there are more speckles currently in the cut-off area of the light cone. A deeper analysis of this is done by Lemke et al. (2011).

The interaction between the various components in a spectrograph causes modal noise patterns in spectra to be strongly dependent on the spectrograph's physical structure. For this reason, it is important to note that the exact patterns will differ for instruments with other designs and sensitivities to these effects.

Part I

Automated Measurement and Analysis of Fiber Properties: Focal Ratio Degradation and Scrambling Gain

This part presents the development and inner mechanism of a fiber measurement and analysis system. All relevant software implementations and hardware configurations were done by me. Unless otherwise stated all figures are based on own measurements and are self-made.

3 Fiber Measurement System

The control software of the measurement setup was written in Python and includes the control of every active piece of hardware used in the setup, except the light sources.

3.1 Setup Overview

The optical setup is split in two basic parts, both shown in figure 3.1. The primary setup handles the control of the light spot, that is coupled into the fiber under test. The first filter wheel carries color filters, with the following options: 400nm, 450nm, 500nm, 600nm, 700nm, 800nm, and also both a closed shutter and an open shutter with no filter. As for the pinhole, mostly a 25 μ m stainless steel pinhole was used.

Currently, the input light source is a white light laser, but it will soon change to a laser-driven light source. This change is practical, as the current light source can not deliver the full spectrum of the available color filters in filter wheel #1. The "Fiber Twist" is used to broaden and to even out the light distribution of the lamp. As seen in Figure 3.2, it consists of a large core fiber which is tightly wound around two cylinders in a figure-eight pattern. This uses the known property of worsening FRD when mechanical stress is applied, ultimately widening the output beam.

After passing through the pinhole, the light is redirected by an off-axis parabola mirror, creating a collimated beam. The second filter wheel then can change the F-ratio of the collimated beam, by acting as interchangeable apertures. There are six machined aluminum apertures mounted in the filter wheel, corresponding to the following approximate focal ratios: 2.5, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0 and 6.0. In measurements, f/2.5 is rarely used, since the input light source tends

Figure 3.1: Sketch of the full optical setup. It is designed to be able to semi-automatically measure the FRD, SG and throughput of a given fiber.

Figure 3.2: Fiber Twist. Apparatus to intentionally stress the fiber to decrease F-ratio through FRD and even out illumination of the input light-beam. The Fiber is a Thorlabs FT200EMT 200 μ m-core fiber with NA = 0.39.

Figure 3.3: Input beam far-field images, the red circle shows the outline of the respective aperture. **Left:** Input beam at $f/2.5$, where the beam barely reaches the outer rim of the aperture. **Right:** Input beam at $f/3.5$, with a more evenly and fully illuminated aperture.

to be uneven in illumination at the outer rim of the beam. This can be seen in Figure 3.3. The light is then directed through a beamsplitter, which serves two purposes. It leads 50% of the light on a photodiode, where it can be used when measuring the fiber throughput. The other portion of light reaches the fiber face of the fiber under test, where then the spot is projected on the fiber core. The Fresnel back-reflection of the spot and the illumination of the fiber core are then going back through the beamsplitter and are captured by camera #1. Figure 2.8 shows both a $25\mu\text{m}$ spot on a $100\mu\text{m}$ circular- and a $89\mu\text{m}$ octagonal-fiber core. The fiber under test is mounted on an x-y-z-tip/tilt stage, which allows to move the fiber to the input spot, while also allowing to change the relative angle of incidence, which is crucial for accurate FRD measurements. The x-axis of this stage can be controlled by a linear motor, which enables automatic image capture for SG measurements, since there the effect of a moving spot is analyzed.

The output connector of the fiber under test can then be mounted on three different positions, depending on the measurement type. In Position #1, the Near-Field (NF) of the fiber is captured, this is used in the Scrambling Gain measurements. Also, this position features an auxiliary lamp that can be used to illuminate the fiber from the other-than-usual side. This helps with finding the fiber core, when trying to align it with the input spot. Position #2 is used for Focal Ratio Degradation measurements or general Far-Field (FF) image captures. Camera #3 is mounted on a linear stage that allows FF image capture at multiple positions, for output F-ratio measurements. This stage is also driven with a linear motor, for automatic FRD measurement. The third position connects directly to a photodiode and is used for throughput measurements.

The stage, where camera #3 is mounted on, and the stage, where the input of the fiber under test is located, are interchangeable. This allows to measure the focal ratios of the input beam to calibrate the input F-ratios for FRD measurements. The interchangeable stages can be seen in Figure 3.4. They use Thorlabs' magnetic bases so that they can be easily swapped.

A detailed list of items used in the setup can be found in Appendix A.

Figure 3.4: The two interchangeable stages. On the left, is a x-y-z-tip/tilt stage, which the fibers are mounted on. On the right, is a y-stage with a large QHYCCD-camera. Both stages are equipped with a linear motor.

3.2 Hardware and Control Software

The integration of several pieces of hardware was achieved in various ways. The photodiodes are read out indirectly via a power-meter from Thorlabs. Filter wheel #1 is controlled via a Thorlabs interface board, which drives a rotational stage. Filter wheel #2 is directly connected with the lab-computer via serial port and controlled using the `pyserial` package. This was done according to the manufacturers protocol, details can be found on the manufacturer's website. Camera #1 and #2 are both thorlabs DCC series cameras. Drivers and SDK are available on the Thorlabs website. Python integration was achieved with the `pylablib.devices.uc480` package. A previous iteration used the `instrumentation-lib` package, which did not allow for control of the cameras pixel rate. This limitation restricted the range of usable exposure times. The third camera is a large detector, a QHY600PH-series device. The large 36mm x 24 mm CCD is necessary to fully detect the Far-Field of the fiber output at multiple distances from the fiber end. Integration was achieved with the SDK available at the QHYCCD website and a publicly available Python wrapper¹. The control of the PI linear stepper motor was also achieved by simple serial bus integration.

The basic structure of the project can be seen in Figure 3.5. The project handles the mentioned hardware integration, but also a graphical user interface, the analysis functions for all measurement types and an automated datasheet generation procedure.

¹Available at <https://github.com/JiangXL/qhyccd-python>

Figure 3.5: Basic software structure, including GUI, modules handling hardware integration and analysis pipelines.

Figure 3.6: FRD calculation procedure. **Left:** Sketch showing how the angle θ_0 is calculated. **Right:** Plot of the linear fit of an example measurement, the calculated output F-ratio for this example was $f/3.66$.

3.3 Automated Functions

The measurement of Focal Ratio Degradation and Scrambling Gain, involves capturing many images with precise changes of certain parameters. Making such measurements for as many fibers as possible naturally leads to automation, not only in processing of the captured images but also in taking them. In the following sections the steps for the automated data capture and analysis will be described in detail.

3.3.1 Focal Ratio Degradation

Theoretical Foundations

As mentioned before, Focal Ratio Degradation refers to the effect of a change of F-ratio between input and output beam of an optical fiber. Measuring this effect requires knowing the F-ratio of the input beam and then measuring the F-ratio of the output beam. For both of these measurements, the radius of the uncollimated beam was measured at three positions, allowing to determine the cone-angle of the beam and thereby the F-ratio. Figure 3.6 shows how the cone angle is measured. The F-ratio then is calculated as followed:

$$f/\# = \frac{1}{2 * slope} \quad (3.1)$$

This is based on the general definition of the F-ratio (See Equation 2.11) and the definition of angle θ_0 (see figure 3.6). A distance to chip value is calculated by utilizing the intercept of the fit and can be applied later for visualization purposes. Its calculation is based on the parameters of the fit:

$$Distance\ to\ Chip = \frac{Intercept}{Slope} \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.7: Flow charts of FRD preparation (**Left**), and measurement procedure (**Right**).

Practical Implementation

Figure 3.7 shows the general procedure for FRD measurements. As for all fiber measurements the fiber has to be connected to the fiber adapter on the x-y-z-tip/tilt stage. Then the fiber core must be aligned with the input spot (e.g. see Figure 2.8). Especially when examining small core fibers, it is helpful to connect the other fiber end to position #1 (see Figure 3.1) and turn on the corresponding lamp. This allows for back-lighting of the fiber and helps with alignment and in initially finding the fiber core. When alignment is done, the fiber is connected to position #2, which is responsible for far-field imaging. This allows to measure the output FF spot size. The angle of incidence of the input beam has a significant contribution to FRD. This means, that it is crucial to align the angle of the fiber adapter correctly with the input beam and thereby minimize the initial output far-field spot radius. For this, typically N.I.N.A.² was used, as it can run the QHYCCD-camera at higher frame-rate than was achievable with the Python integration. The minimization then is a simple process of adjusting tip/tilt and checking the size until the size is minimized. Now that all physical preparations are done, the measurement can be started via the GUI, after reviewing the check-list. The checks for an FRD measurements include, making sure that the fiber is connected to the correct camera and that the exposure time is set appropriately.

The measuring procedure iterates over five input beam F-ratios (F/3.5, F/4, F/4.5, F/5,

²Nighttime Imaging 'N' Astronomy

Figure 3.8: Color filter wheel, or filter wheel #1. Contains the following filters: 400nm, 450nm, 500nm, 600nm, 700nm, 800nm, as well as open and closed shutters.

Figure 3.9: Example of Far-Field images with center of mass and circle of 98% encircled energy marked. **Left:** Far-Field image of input beam. **Right:** Far-Field image of output beam.

F/6) and three camera positions respectively. Then the shutter is closed and dark frames are taken for each position and F-ratio individually. This is done to eliminate position sensitive stray-light contamination. The shutter is part of filter-wheel #1 (see Figure 3.8). This is achieved by simply utilizing a cap to block the light for a closed shutter and leaving a spot without filter for an open shutter. After the capturing process is done, the analysis can be started manually via the GUI. It was intentionally designed not to start the analysis immediately, for multiple reasons. The raw data is saved to the internal lab-server which allows analysis from another machine, while doing other measurements in the lab. Also it allows to do more measurements in the same amount of time, while leaving the analysis for a later instance, which is beneficial since all the lights in the lab need to be out to ensure good results. This of course means that other work in the lab needs to be halted for that period of time, so minimizing this is in the interest of everyone.

The analysis procedure is as follows: First the images are reduced, which in this case consists only of dark subtraction. Then the center of mass of the output FF image spot is calculated, using the `skimage.measure` package to find the center of mass and then fitting a circle so that

98% encircled energy are inside that circle. An example of this can be seen in Figure 3.9. To ensure consistency, the value 98% encircled energy is also used when measuring the F-ratios of the input beam. The obtained radii at the predefined camera positions are then used according to Figure 3.6 for calculating the output F-ratio at each input $f/\#$.

3.3.2 Scrambling Gain

Theoretical foundations

Scrambling Gain is usually measured by comparing the relative displacement of the center of mass (COM) of input and output (See Equation 2.12). Since the SG value can change depending on the input spot position, a series of measurements is taken with several positions across the fiber. While the formula is quite straightforward, obtaining these parameters from the input and output NF images is not trivial. First a value for the core-center of the fiber is acquired. This is done by fitting a mask, shaped like the fiber core, on the input and output NF images. The creation of rectangular masks is done by simple array operations, i.e. defining x, y start and endpoints and setting all values within to one. More complex shapes are created with the `skimage.draw` package by either using the `disk` function for circles or defining vertices as input for the `polygon` function to create octagons. Potentially this can easily be done for any shape, but since circular, rectangular and octagonal core shapes are most common, these are the most useful. This approach also allows the measurement of more exotic shapes, like "stadium" and D-shaped cores (see Figure 3.12), since they do not deviate much from the common shapes and the template fit works for them reliably. To fit these masks, the image is first prepared to make detection easier. Canny edge detection (Canny 1986) from the `skimage` package is used to highlight the edges of the core. Since there sometimes are irregularities at the edges, mostly in the input images originating from the relatively bright input spot, potential breaks in the outline of the edge are closed by running the edge-image through two iterations of dilation and erosion. After this, the outlines are filled to eliminate potential effects of outlines remaining within the fiber core. Then the mask is matched to the resulting image by template-matching via the `cv2` package. An example of the whole matching process is shown in Figure 3.10. This procedure proves to also be reliable for images, where the spot is placed on the edge of the core, and consequently distorts the core shape, as seen in Figure 3.11. The center of the matched mask is then used in further calculations.

To record the input spot position, a simple COM detection approach is used. To eliminate the influence of the fiber-face in the COM calculation, when detecting the spot position, a threshold is applied to narrow down the area of interest to the spot. Because the optical setup is such, that the spot does not move relative to the camera, the median of the COM value for each position is used in further calculations. In the output images the COM detection is utilized the same way, which now detects the barycenter of the output Near-Field. With all these measurements complete, the COM values are first referenced relative to the fiber core. This is done because the input fiber core moves with each measurement relative to the camera, and comparing COM values without this reference would return biased results. In the output, where the fiber does not move, the calculation is still done to suppress errors due to instability

Figure 3.10: Steps for template matching and to create a mask of the fiber core. The mask is created and matched like this for every in- and output image of the measurement. **(A)** Initial reduced entrance image. **(B)** Binary edge image, created with canny edge detection. **(C)** Edges after two iterations of dilation and erosion. **(D)** Binary-filled edges. **(E)** Fitted best-match template. **(F)** Best match on original image.

Figure 3.11: Matching procedure, similar to Figure 3.10, but with spot distorting the detected core geometry. **(A)** Initial reduced entrance image. **(B)** Binary filled image after edge detection and two iterations of dilation and erosion. **(C)** Template-matched mask to original image.

Figure 3.12: Microscope images of two different fiber ends after the last step of polishing. **Left:** "Stadium"-fiber. **Right:** D-shaped fiber, with illuminated core.

of the setup. A reference measurement then is chosen from the gauged values, based on which is closest to the fiber core. This is done to establish a reference point in the Near- and Far-Field measurements. The displacement values for Formula 2.12 are then calculated as the difference of the gauged COM values from each measurement to the reference measurement. This then leads to the final SG values. The SG_{min} value,

$$SG_{min} = \frac{\max(d_i/D_i)}{\max(d_o/D_o)} \quad (3.3)$$

proposed by Sutherland et al. (2016) is also calculated, since the SG value, as defined in 2.12, is not constant for different spot offsets. This also simplifies comparison across fibers, without having to compare measurements across all spot positions. Some plots of the results are part of the fiber datasheet example in Appendix B.

Practical Implementation

The preparation for the Scrambling Gain measurement is somewhat similar to the FRD preparation. The spot still needs to be aligned with the fiber core, but because the other fiber end needs to be connected to position #1 anyway, there is no additional work needed to achieve back-lighting if necessary. Tip/tilt need to be adjusted if not already done, since bad FRD helps the scrambling and influences results.

For this measurement the spot should be moved to the center of the fiber, while the motor controller, which is connected to the x, y, z-stage for SG measurements, is at the 5mm mark. This serves as the initial positioning layout for the SG measurement. Since this measurement uses two cameras (Camera #1 and #2, in Figure 3.1), both exposure times need to be set accordingly. When setting the exposure times, it should be made sure, that the whole fiber core is visible, since the illuminated core is needed for the analysis to work. This can be problematic in large core fibers, because the flux density of the back-lighting is lower. The subsequent raising of the exposure time, can lead to overexposure of the spot, which lowers accuracy. After checking the other items on the GUI checklist, the measurement is ready to be started.

The measurement itself is straightforward, depending on the fiber core diameter and the desired number of positions, i.e. the number of different SG measurements, the linear motor drives the stage along the x-axis in equidistant steps. The step size is calculated, so that the whole diameter of the core is covered in the desired number of positions. At each position one input and one output Near-Field image are taken with camera #1 and #2 (see Figure 3.1) respectively. These are then reduced with dark-frames and ready for analysis. The analysis is started again separately using the GUI.

3.3.3 Throughput

The throughput measurement utilizes the two photodiodes shown in Figure 3.1. These are read out using a power-meter doing around 100 readings per filter. Since the first photodiode measures the half of the input beam, which is reflected by the beamsplitter, a calibration

measurement was done to check its performance with each filter applied. In the throughput analysis the calibration measurement is then used to correct for the effects of the beamsplitter.

3.4 Other Additional Features

Next to the main measurements, that can be controlled with the GUI, there are some other implemented features to help with calibration or visualization.

General Hardware Control

For purposes of testing or preparation, all of the hardware can be controlled manually via the GUI. Examples include: Switching the color filters, controlling the F-ratio of the beam, moving the linear motor to specific positions or capturing test-images with all cameras to work out a fitting exposure time.

Calibration Measurements

As before mentioned, for some measurement types it is necessary to do calibrations. To check the input F-ratios for the fibers, it is possible to swap camera #3 with the x-y-z stage of the fiber input, to make a "System F-ratio Measurement". This then goes through mostly the same steps of the regular FRD measurement, with the difference that the camera now picks up the input beam instead of the fiber output. Examples of the images taken in this position, can be seen in Figure 3.3. This measurement is sensible to do, especially after changes to the setup have been made. An example measurement can be seen in Figure 3.13.

Another calibration measurement is done for throughput. As mentioned before, the beamsplitter has to be tested, since the first photodiode only measures the flux deflected by it. For this the second photodiode needs to be mounted to the fiber-facing beamsplitter output. The throughput calibration can then be started using the GUI and a calibration file is created, containing the relative flux values for each wavelength. This file can then be selected when starting the analysis for a throughput measurement.

Visualization

For some cases, it can be interesting to compare the input NF with the resulting output FF. For this case there is a function which drives the spot along the fiber similar to what is done in the SG measurement, while capturing the change in the FF. This can be used to check if a fiber carries light in outer layers, since there are instances of fibers with multiple claddings which can display this behavior. A result of this can be seen as part of Appendix B.

Another example of an additional visualization feature is the function, which captures FF images for each color filter. This can be done to determine if there is any dependence on input beam wavelength.

3.5 Graphical User Interface

As mentioned before the GUI is used to control the optical setup for general measurements, calibrations or other test. As can be seen in Figure 3.14, it is made up of four tabs for measuring,

Figure 3.13: A plot showing how the new and old input beam F-ratios compare. Plot style is the same as for general FRD measurements, where output and input refers to in and out of the fiber. Output f/# in this case are the new system values, input f/# are the old system values. For this calibration measurement, there was only a slight change in the values of around f/3.5 and f/6.

Figure 3.14: Images of graphical user interface. **Left:** Main interaction window. **Right:** Fiber data window, for setting fiber parameters and metadata.

Figure 3.15: Numbering scheme for fibers. It consists of the core shape and diameter or dimensions, the number of the fiber for multiple with same parameters and the number of the measurement, in case multiple measurements with the same fiber are done. The full extent of this scheme is used for folder names, while the measurement number is omitted on the tag of the physical fiber.

analysis, running auxiliary functions and camera control respectively. When first measuring a fiber, the associated fiber parameters have to be entered in the "Fiber Data"-window (see Figure 3.14, right). The required parameters for a measurement include: Fiber Name, Fiber Shape (meaning the core shape, i.e. circular, octagonal or rectangular) and Fiber (core) Diameter. Everything else is optional but serves the purpose of thorough documentation and can add to a better understanding of fiber effects. When saving these parameters, a folder on the internal lab-server is created with the fiber name. While working with different fibers, a naming convention has been established, shown in Figure 3.15. This scheme ensures consistent naming and tracking across repeated measurements. All measurement types are stored in the same fiber folder. The measurement number was added to the numbering scheme, since repeated measurements of the same fiber can be necessary for testing, adjustments or if something failed.

Because of the measurement storage on the lab-server, the analysis can optionally be done from another machine. In that case, an existing folder from the server can be chosen and the analysis can be run with that data. Among other things, this is useful for code improvements and maintenance, which therefore do not have to be done in the lab directly.

3.6 Automated Report Generation with Quarto

When analysis of the desired measurements is done, the automated report generation can be started. This uses Quarto³, to render a Jupyter Notebook, containing the layout of the report template. This system automatically collects all the results and visualizations, that are available from the selected fiber and displays them in a pdf-file. An example of this can be seen in Appendix B.

³<https://quarto.org>

4 Fiber preparation

To be able to measure fibers in the first place, the bare fibers need to be polished and for better handling they need to be assembled with furcation tubing and fiber ferrules. Exceptions are made, when testing how the application of a ferrule, which includes applying epoxy to the bare fiber-cladding, affects the FRD of a fiber. Since typically epoxy shrinks while curing, the fiber is exposed to mechanical stress, which is a common cause of FRD. Furcation tubing is designed to relieve some of the stress of bending and protects the fiber generally. It can be sensible to not be used, when intentionally putting a fiber under stress to benefit from the improved scrambling ability, if FRD is not relevant. An example would be the "fiber twist" (see Figure 3.2), whose purpose is to enlarge and even out the light beam coming from the light source.

4.1 Assembly

Fiber assembly, in this case, means to equip the fibers with connectors and furcation tubing. Since there is a multitude of fiber connectors with various styles and ferrule-bore diameters available, it is important to choose the best fitting one, depending on the fiber and the purpose. Most commonly used in our lab are simple FC/PC connectors with mostly ceramic ferrules. The ferrule bore diameter should be chosen to be as small as possible, while still bigger than the cladding. The gap between bare fiber cladding and the fiber ferrule, where the fiber then sits in, is filled with epoxy. If the gap is too wide, this can cause issues in polishing and for FRD performance, since the more epoxy is used, the more stress is applied to the fiber due to shrinking.

A difficult assembly step is stripping the fiber from its coating. There are many available tools to physically rip the coating from the fiber, but a preferred option may be to do so chemically. For polyimide coating, the coating can be burned off using an open flame, and subsequently cleaned with isopropyl alcohol. While this can work for acrylate also, using paint stripper might be a less radical alternative. Here a small drop to the tip of the fiber and waiting for a while is enough to weaken the coating to be easily removed by hand. After stripping the fiber, it should be tested that it fits into the ferrule and that the length of fiber extending out of the ferrule is satisfactory. The epoxy application is the last step to assembly and can have a large influence in the fiber performance. EPO-TEK 301-2 was used, which was proposed by Oliveira, L. De Oliveira, and J. Dos Santos (2005) to be the best fitting epoxy for this application. Since only a small amount of epoxy is needed for assembly, it is helpful to store the remaining mixture in the freezer. This will prevent the epoxy from curing and allow it to remain usable for days or weeks.

An example of how the fiber sits in the connector ferrule can be seen in Figure 3.12. The shown fiber ends are also examples for imperfect ferrule sizes, since there is a large amount of glue filling in the space between ferrule and fiber cladding, especially for the D-shaped fiber.

Figure 4.1: Fiber polishing steps. From top left to bottom right: Fiber end after polishing with 9 μm , 3 μm , 1 μm and 0.01 μm grit polishing films. Fiber is the same as shown in Figure 3.12 (right). Note that the core of the fiber is not visible here, because there is no backlighting.

4.2 Polishing

For polishing, diamond polishing films in 30 μm , 9 μm , 3 μm , 1 μm and a final polishing film in 0.01 μm grit, was used. The general process, that is described in the Thorlabs manual¹ was followed. The whole process is difficult to do in a exactly reproducible manner. Largely I relied on checking the polishing progress of each step with a microscope. Then I would either proceed to the next step or continue polishing, depending on how the surface looks. Figure 4.1 shows the finished state of the fiber face, after each step. In this case, the fiber ferrule had an imperfect size, as it was much larger than the fiber cladding. This makes it easy for epoxy residue, to be wiped over the fiber face and penetrate the perimeter of the fiber cladding or even the core. This does not necessarily affect performance if the fiber core is still clear, but it creates an additional hurdle during polishing.

¹Direct link to the pdf. Otherwise available as product "FN96A" on [thorlabs.com](https://www.thorlabs.com).

5 Results

In this chapter we present some results of the fiber measurements, that were done with the automated set-up. We will have a look at a general overview of the SG and FRD behavior of 15 fibers. The two measurements were done for most but not all of these fibers, exceptions occur partly because SG measurements are difficult to do for small core fibers.

All measurements were done as discussed in Section 3.3.

5.1 FRD

Figure 5.1 shows the combined FRD results of all measured fibers. Based on that data it is difficult to claim any apparent trends towards any physical fiber property. Since FRD is mainly induced by physical stress, results like these may not only depend on the fiber itself, but surely are also altered by the assembly process. Especially vital is the application of the connectors. The tested fibers are from very different sources and similar assembly conditions cannot be guaranteed at all. Nonetheless this could resemble real-world conditions and comparative results can still be valid.

In Figure 5.1 (left) the fiber C_18 appears twice. It was measured with both a 10 μ m and a 25 μ m pinhole, with significantly different results. A likely cause is that, since the 25 μ m spot is larger than the fiber core, there is some light being guided by the cladding surrounding the core and widening the output beam. This is an effect, that has to be carefully avoided to not alter the results.

Three different circular 100 μ m-core fibers were measured, one of which is significantly worse than the others. This might be due to a bad connector application or another physical but invisible imperfection.

These two examples illustrate how sensitive FRD is and how difficult it is to obtain accurate results.

All fibers seem to have an almost linear relationship of input vs. output focal ratio. This may be the case in the tested regime up to F6, but Lee et al. (2024) show, that the relationship will become non-linear for slower beams.

Figure 5.1: Input vs. output focal ratio for all fibers. Fiber names follow this system: "C" Circular core, "O" Octagonal core, "R" Rectangular core, "S" Square core. The directly following number indicates dimension, i.e. diameter or length of the sides. In the case of the C_18 fibers the last part indicate whether the fiber was measured with a 10 or 25 μm pinhole, in other cases it is just to distinguish between different fibers with the same dimensions.

Fiber Designation	SG_{min}	Fiber Designation	SG_{min}
C_50_1	90	O_100	751
C_100_0	125	R_33x132	159
C_100_1	50	R_40x120	384
C_100_2	59	R_45x180	573
O_40	194	S_50	160
O_50_1	47		

Table 5.1: Scrambling gain value for all tested fibers. SG_{min} calculated according to Equation 3.3.

5.2 SG

Table 5.1 show the scrambling gain results of all tested fibers. There are some clear expected trends regarding the core shape. As already firmly established in the literature (See e.g.: Lee et al. 2024; Avila 2012; Julian Stürmer, Christian Schwab, et al. 2016), non-circular core shapes have much better scrambling performance than circular ones. This is because circular fibers usually produce a circular structure in the near-field, as seen in Figure 2.8. Any structure in the output near-field of a fiber is an inhomogeneity and therefore the exact opposite of what is necessary for good scrambling performance.

In Table 5.1, there is one fiber that breaks the general expectation. The O_50_1 fiber has, despite being octagonal and therefore usually performing well, very bad SG. Figure 5.2 shows the results of that fiber in more detail. The upper plot shows the whole set of datapoints used to judge the SG. As already mentioned in Section 3.3, we measure the displacement of the output center of mass (COM) with respect to the input spot position. The plot shows that

Figure 5.2: SG plot showing the performance of the O_50_1 fiber with $SG_{min} = 45$. The bottom show the exit near-field of the same fiber at 6 equidistant input spot positions beginning at the far left and ending with the spot in the center of the fiber face. Clearly there is a distinct star structure forming the further the spot wanders into the middle of the fiber entrance. This is a sign for bad SG performance as shown by the plot on top.

none of datapoints are within the range of SG of 200. The images at the bottom are some of the exit near field images, that are used to measure the COM displacement. The leftmost image is the results of injection at the edge of the fiber entrance and the image series progresses in equidistant steps towards central injection in the rightmost image. There clearly appears a star structure in the core. This, similarly to the ring structure in circular fibers, results in bad SG performance.

The reason for the appearance of this structure is unclear, but likely a result of the manufacturing.

Figure 5.3 shows the full SG plot for one of the worst and one of the best tested fibers. One can clearly see now, why a single or even a few measurements and their SG values are hardly representative of the general SG performance, justifying the use of the SG_{min} value. The bad SG example in the left plot, shows how severely the SG value changes depending on the input spot position. The variability of the well performing fiber in the plot on the right is much lower in comparison.

Figure 5.3: Examples for full scrambling gain plots. We plot the movement of the spot on the entrance fiber face vs. the displacement of the center of mass (COM) of the exit fiber face. Following Equation 2.12, we marked the regions within SG of at least 200, 500 or 2000 is achieved. We have three sets of datapoints, differentiating between movement in X- or Y-direction and total movement. SG_{min} calculations are based on total movement.

Left: Fiber with one of the worst SG capabilities: C_100_1 with $SG_{min} = 50$

Right: Fiber with one of the best SG capabilities: O_100 with $SG_{min} = 751$

6 Conclusion

The measurement of Focal Ratio Degradation and Scrambling Gain properties of fibers are vital to ensure precise measurements of the spectrographs utilizing those fibers. FRD directly influences spectrograph throughput, and SG the mitigation of guiding and seeing variations. Only if these factors are well-known, can the design-goal of a spectrograph be assured. 2ES and MARVEL use a multitude of fibers with differing characteristics to try and maximize their utility in the spectrograph. Scrambling performance and Modal Noise impact have to be balanced while keeping FRD minimal. The fibers are chosen based on known connections of the physical and optical fiber properties, but before they can be installed the fibers have to be characterized to ensure they meet their set thresholds. The developed automated fiber measurement and analysis system is capable of doing these measurements reliably and with ensured repeatability. Beyond that, it enables fiber measurements in large quantities. This serves the purpose of discovering new or strengthening known connections between fiber performance and their physical layout. The system fills the gap of non-standardized fiber measurements, which make comparison on large scales impossible.

Automated measurements solve uncertainties of human-bias, day-to-day variations or positional precision. Routines apply the same thresholds, fits, criteria on exposure times, and other otherwise intuition biased parameters if done by humans. Fixed calibration workflows ensure that the same conditions are met for every measurement. Motor controlled stages exercise micron precision, far surpassing manual manipulation.

The system is capable of generating datasheets on the press of of a button, providing quick, distributable summaries of the fiber's performance. The modular parts of the setup allow for easy recalibrations, ensuring precision even after adjusting or changing things about the setup. Limitations of precision are the still manual tip-tilt adjustments at the fiber entrance. Misalignment of the fibers and the input beams optical axes can significantly worsen the measured FRD. Additionally the setup is sensitive towards stray light, limiting its precision depending on the brightness of the setups environment. Extreme fiber core sizes, are difficult to measure both in too small and too large. The pinhole size poses a lower limit because it is difficult to guarantee controlled spot movement and positioning if the spot is larger than the fiber. FRD can be affected if the fiber cladding also guides light. A spot that is too large would couple light into the cladding, which would significantly worsen the FRD. Camera saturation issues constrain the maximum size of measurable fibers, at least for SG measurements. This is because the core has to be detectable on the fiber entrance near-field, without overexposing the spot. In case of large core fibers, the core illumination from the back-reflection at the fiber output is spread over a larger fiber core area, leaving the core harder to see against the bright spot in the fiber entrance.

From the measured fibers results that were presented, some known trends become apparent. Clearly average Scrambling Gain values for circular fibers are much lower, than those for octagonal or rectangular fiber cores. Regarding FRD, it is clear that the degradation of focal ratio is worse for slower beams. In fact the relation for input and output F-number is nearly linear in most cases, at least in the utilized range of F-ratios. It was also shown that even for nominally identical fibers or fibers with closely matching physical attributes, differences of manufacturing, polishing or connectorization can lead to vastly differing optical properties. It was shown that three instances of a circular 100 μm fibers can have significantly different FRD performances. Similarly in regards to SG a 40 micron octagonal fiber exhibited four-times better SG performance than a 50 micron octagonal fiber. Here the worse fiber suffered from structured illumination at its exit, likely due to issues in manufacturing. This highlights the importance of checking a fiber's performance before using them.

Improvements can be made to the setup enclosure to mitigate the influence of stray light. This would also allow the lab to be used independently of whether a measurement is running, since light would have to be turned off. Clearly, an automated gimbal mount for tip-tilt adjustments at the fiber entrance would simplify and accelerate the measurement workflow. It would also eliminate the largest source of human bias and improve the system's precision. To further improve the measurements, one could install an adjustable aperture instead of the currently installed filter-wheel with multiple fixed apertures. This would not only extend the range of input F-ratios available, but also allow for measurements with very small step-sizes in input F-number. This would be easily implemented in the automated measurement cycle and provide smooth input-vs-output F-ratio plots, for much more detailed analysis and wider F-number ranges. Additionally small adjustments can be made, e.g. improving the input beam uniformity by installing a diffuser or swapping the near-field cameras for higher resolution ones to improve accuracy.

Future instruments, especially 2ES and MARVEL, benefit from this work, as it provides guidance and reassurance about the abilities of the planned fibers. Fiber performance reports can be delivered quickly and with minimal human intervention. This enables large scale data accumulation, providing a robust foundation for optical fiber testing and research.

Part II

Measurement and Analysis of Modal Noise

This part presents the measurement and analysis of Modal Noise at the Waltz spectrograph at the LSW. Software implementations and analysis pipelines were done by me, figures are produced based on own measurements.

7 Measurement Setup

To realistically measure deviations in spectra, we take several flat images with a LED. Ideally we would expect the flats to be smooth and without any deviations, but in reality however we find fluctuations, with various spatial and therefore spectral frequency-modulations.

The measurement setup consists of three main parts: the input device, the fiber under test, and the spectrograph. The input device, depending on the measurement, can be a simple light source or a system controlling the input beam of the fiber entrance directly. With the input-setup, shown in Figure 7.1, parameters like the Focal Ratio, input spot size and input spot position are regulated.

Some measurements were done comparing spectra with agitated or static fiber. Agitation was carried out by stretching and compressing the rolled up fiber with a frequency of about 0.5Hz . Spectrometry was handled by the Waltz spectrograph at the LSW, with either direct connection between test fiber and spectrograph or connection via an additional $33 \times 132\mu\text{m}$ fiber between test fiber and spectrograph.

All details for the spectrograph can be found in Tala et al. (2016). The spectrograph has a maximum resolution of about $R = 65000$, with a wavelength range of about 450-800nm. The 50 orders, we are using give us an effective range of 450-750nm. We cut a few orders because of some unreliable and noisy data at the red end.

7.1 Input Setup

The input setup, also shown in Figure 7.1, allows for control of spot size, F-ratio and spot position. F-ratio is set to $F/3$ and spot size to $10\mu\text{m}$ for all measurements. Spot positions are alternated between "edge" and "middle". These positions are shown in Figure 7.2, with the example of an $100\mu\text{m}$ fiber. In the case of a few fibers, the spot is larger than the fiber itself. Here, the spot is placed so that still only the edge of the fiber core is illuminated. With the single-mode fiber, there is no edge injection.

Figure 7.1: Input-setup for input spot size, focal ratio and spot position control.

Figure 7.2: Fiber injection spot positions for a 100µm circular fiber. Middle and edge.

Figure 7.3: Agitation machine. The arm moves with a maximum frequency of about 0.5Hz left and right. The full travel span are then about 10cm , resulting in significant compression and stretching of the coiled fiber.

Agitation was done using an improvised agitation machine, seen in Figure 7.3. It has a amplitude of about 10cm and a maximum frequency of about 0.5Hz .

The light source for fiber injection is a Thorlabs MCWHL5. Its spectrum can be seen in Figure 7.4, which of course leads to the échelle power-distribution adopting a similar pattern. This pattern will be visible in every measurement and impacts analysis in terms of deviating shot noise influences in-between orders.

Figure 7.4: Light source spectra on CCD and from Thorlabs spec-sheet (Thorlabs 2024). Upper and blue end of the échelle spectrum is at about 450nm, lower and red end is at about 800nm.

8 Analysis

Analysis was done with a mostly self written python reduction and analysis pipeline. For the extraction of the spectra, code from the Maroon-X project was reused and changed to fit the Waltz data.

Although the Waltz has its own data reduction pipeline, we opted for a more modular approach since we exchanged the spectrograph fiber during the measurements, which changes the spectral format. Additionally we didn't require full data reduction.

For the calculation of the wavelength solution, a dynamic time warp (DTW) approach with the underlying dtw-python¹ package was adopted. Giorgino (2009) provides more information about DTW.

Generally all five before mentioned fibers are included in each measurement. A few exceptions are: The 460B-fiber was not measured in "edge"-configuration, and both the M64- and the C18-fiber, were not measured in the indirect time-series configuration.

8.1 Spectrum Extraction

A raw flat spectrum can be seen in Figure 7.4. Parts of the Maroon-X extraction pipeline are used to fit polynomials to each order. These polynomials are then labeled and fed back into the pipeline as masks with a given line thickness, usually 10 pixels. For each order we then get an image the size of the original with one order isolated, ready for further analysis. Figure 8.1 shows some of the steps for spectrum extraction. First the orders of a consistently used flatfield image are traced, then the positional data is used to identify the same stripes in the dark-subtracted science image. The usage of the same flatfield image for all measurements guarantees consistent positional recognition and labels in further processing. The resulting extracted spectrum then always has a size of 50×2048 pixels, comprised of the 50 extracted orders with each 2048 pixels length in dispersion direction. This then is the basis of all further analysis.

¹<https://github.com/DynamicTimeWarping/dtw-python>

Figure 8.1: Traced, identified and extracted spectrum. **Left:** Traced stripes, input: Log-scaled flatfield. **Right:** Identified stripes, input: dark-subtracted science image, and positional data from traced stripes. **Bottom:** Extracted spectrum, 50×2048 pixels, 50 échelle orders stacked in y-direction, 2048px CCD width. (Not the original aspect ratio.)

Figure 8.2: Raw log-scale Thorium-Argon échelle-spectrum. Bottom or red end, shows some overexposed Argon lines.

8.2 Dynamical Time Warp Wavelength Solution

For the calculation of the wavelength solution of the spectrograph we primarily used the `pyKosmos`² package, with a custom wrapper. As reference served a Thorium-Argon (ThAr) lamp, of which a raw spectrum can be seen in Figure 8.2. Some of the stronger lines in the red end or bottom of the spectrum are clearly overexposed. As not to disturb the DTW fit too much with these lines, each order is checked for overexposed lines and they get filtered. They are replaced by an artificial approximate expectation of what the line would look like without the bleeding effects that overexposure comes with. An example of that can be seen in Figure 8.3 (Top).

Before any orders can be fit to a reference spectrum, the reference needs to be prepared too. This is not a trivial task, as it includes estimating the free spectral range (FSR) seen on the detector, and the relative counts of each ThAr line population. This was achieved by following an iterative process of trial and error. As basis for the FSR served the blaze angle and grating constant, plugged into the grating equation and solved for wavelength, we then get Equation 2.6. Equation 2.5 defines the FSR of a diffraction grating. Since the spectral range on the detector is wider, due to overlap regions, this gives only a rough estimate. With the help of the group of overexposed lines, which are strong Argon lines, the detector FSR could be constrained further after some trying and testing. When the wavelength-range per order is set, the reference data is adjusted to the resolving power of the spectrograph, to make the reference spectrum physically similar to the instrumental response.

After these preparations, the spectrum can be fit per-order using DTW alignment, seen in Figure 8.3 (Center). There are numerous constraints that can be used to perfect the alignment,

²<https://github.com/jradavenport/pykosmos>

in our case we use a Sakoe-Chiba band (See Sakoe and Chiba 2003, for details) as a global constraint and a symmetric, normalized step pattern as local constraint.

A good representation of how these constraints act on the alignment can be seen in Figure 8.3 (Bottom). Important to note is that, when the Sakoe-Chiba band is used the amount of data points for reference and measured data should be similar, since the band is designed around fitting data points one-to-one and a large difference in resolution of the two datasets could lead to the real alignment path being outside of the band.

After the DTW alignment, one only needs to fit the aligned peaks with a polynomial, while filtering for gross outliers for better consistency, and the wavelength solution is done. The implementation how it is now has slight precision issues of up to 0.5\AA in some edge areas of orders. For what it is being used in this project we expect the precision to be largely sufficient, particularly since precision only drops in edge areas, where data is mostly dominated by shot noise anyways.

8.3 Static vs. Agitated Fibers

The first measurements focus on the differences of a Static vs. Agitated fiber and on changes in the input spot position. Important to note is that all measurements in this section were done while the fiber under test was not directly connected to the spectrograph, but rather coupled to a 33×132 fiber that is normally used to carry the light from the Waltz telescope to its respective spectrograph. While this results in indirect measurements of the test fiber, qualitative differences can still be made out.

Injection was done in two states: Middle and Edge. With a spot size of $10\mu\text{m}$ and an injection beam focal ratio of $F/3$. The spot size was kept constant for all measurements. Therefore in the case of testing a $100\mu\text{m}$ core, the fiber was underfilled and in the case of the M64L02 fiber, which has a core of about $8.2\mu\text{m}$ the fiber was overfilled. The two injection states can be seen in Figure 7.2. Agitation was done using the agitation machine, shown in Figure 7.3. For each possible combination of agitation state and injection state, five images or spectra were captured, plus dark images.

8.4 Time Series

We were initially inspired by the work of Oliva et al. (2019), where they investigated the change of a spectrum with time and with fiber state. We did the same measurement for multiple fibers to highlight dependency on the number of excited modes. For this, the fibers were first connected indirectly to the spectrograph, with the 33×132 fiber in between, and at the other end directly connected to the light source. In this measurement the test fiber was always overfilled. But in the case of indirect connection the 33×132 spectrograph-fiber is often underfilled, since we are connecting few micron fibers with a much larger one.

Figure 8.3: Some steps from the DTW alignment process used for the wavelength solution of the spectrograph. All plots are from the alignment of the same order of the échelle spectrum. **Top:** Preparation of the arc spectrum with overexposed peaks.

Center: DTW alignment, the grey lines indicate which part of the arc spectrum is aligned to which part of the reference spectrum.

Bottom: Illustration of the underlying principle behind DTW alignment for one order. The blue stripe is the path of minimal cost, satisfying all constrains. The wider colored band, is a result of the Sakoe-Chiba constraint. For details of this plot please refer to Giorgino (2009, "Three-way plotting")

Figure 8.4: Example of a SOTS (Single-order time-series) image. Each line is the same échelle order, but taken from consecutive images of a time-series. This highlights time-scale and severity of noise in the spectra. Both pixel and wavelength axes are given, y-axis is in images. In this example, the time between images was one minute, so the y-axis is the same in minutes.

8.4.1 General Analysis

We tested multiple capture frequencies and time series lengths. In the end, we decided on one image per minute over a period of mostly one hour. The raw images are all dark subtracted and their orders extracted. The extracted orders are then collapsed in y-direction or cross dispersion direction to get a single line of 2048 pixels for each order. Images are then handled in the format of one order per line, with the red end at the bottom, and the whole CCD pixel range in horizontal direction. For a whole spectrum, 50 orders are extracted, leading to image sizes of 50×2048 pixels. The usual analysis pipeline then calculates a mean image over the time axis. In the case of one image per minute over the course of one hour, for example, that would lead to a mean image composed of these 60 images. Then all images are divided by the mean image, correcting for the blaze and highlighting changes in time.

To highlight differences within one order, we constructed images each containing the time evolution of one single order. An example can be seen in Figure 8.4, here each line is the same order taken from one image each in the time series. Now time changes with the y-coordinate, with the beginning of the time series at the bottom. These images were dubbed single order time-series (SOTS).

8.4.2 Wide format

Additionally we analyzed the spectra that have not been fully collapsed, i.e. summed up in cross-dispersion direction. We take the raw échelle spectrum, straighten each order and cut them out to a width of a few pixels.

An example of the finished product can be seen in Figure 8.5. This provides us with the possibility to detect changes in between images in the time-series with spatial features in cross-dispersion direction also.

Figure 8.5: Same as Figure 8.4 but in wide format. Previously, each original order was collapsed into one line. Now, each order is extracted as-is into a six-pixel-wide stripe. For this each order is straightened, which then results in some vertical faults, e.g. at ca. 1100px.

8.4.3 Histogram Analysis

To confirm that the noise in the spectra are not just due to shot or detector noise, we analyze the statistics of the reduced data. We use the raw counts to calculate the expected noise and fit the histogram of the measured noise. The difference of the two then gives insight on the noise profile.

Specifically we use the SOTS images as base, then extract the count distribution as a histogram to fit a Gaussian. As mentioned before, in case of the SOTS images each order is already divided by a mean. Therefore the distribution is centered around one and permanent structures, as the blaze, have no influence on the histogram. Also, since in the SOTS images all images of the time-series are included, the histogram is based on around 60 images, depending on the series. The shot noise model is based on the original counts of the collapsed stripes, simply calculated as:

$$\sigma_{shot} = \frac{\sqrt{N}}{g} \quad (8.1)$$

with N being the Number of counts and g being the gain of the spectrograph CCD, which is $g = 1.2$ for the Waltz CCD. The standard deviation values for fit- and model- noise are then subtracted,

$$\sigma_{res} = \sqrt{\sigma_{fit}^2 - \sigma_{shot}^2} \quad (8.2)$$

to get a residual noise value.

Figure 8.6: Example of an image of per-order Fourier transforms. Each line is the FT of one order of the original image. Order numbers rise towards the blue-end.

8.4.4 Fourier Analysis

In terms of Fourier analysis, we were again initially inspired by Oliva et al. (2019). The initial analysis was done by extracting the orders one by one and correcting for the blaze using a Savitzky-Golay filter with large window, set to 50% of the size of the data array. The raw data was then divided by the resulting fit, leading to a distribution around unity. Afterwards for each of these arrays ranging over 2048 pixels, the Fourier transform (FT) was calculated. This was done utilizing the `Numpy` fast Fourier transforms (FFT). The resulting set of FTs, were then mean combined and linearly fitted in log-space using the same fit function as Oliva et al. (2019).

$$DFT_{MN} = 10^a \cdot 10^{-s \cdot v} \quad (8.3)$$

Here, when thinking in log-space, a acts as the intercept and s as the slope of the line.

For the time series, we adopted a per-order system for Fourier analysis. To inspect the nature of the measured noise, we utilize the FT again along dispersion direction of the spectrograph in each order. As basis for the FT served the normalized collapsed stripe images, created along the general pipeline process. Here every line is one échelle order and each line is already normalized by the mean image over time, canceling permanent structures like the blaze. Then for every order again the FT is calculated using FFT and put together in one image for convenience. This leads to one image for each input image, where y is still the order, with red being at the bottom, but x is now the Fourier frequency, starting at zero with the background value. An example can be seen in Figure 8.6.

9 Results

9.1 Static vs. Agitated

This measurement is based on indirect connection to the spectrograph and light injection with a $10\mu\text{m}$ spot. For each fiber and fiber state five images were taken with exposure-times of 30 seconds, except for the single-mode 460B, where the exposure-time was raised to 180s to compensate for the loss of light.

Statistical Noise Analysis

Figure 9.1 (Left) shows the results of a simple noise analysis. In this case noise was measured as a mean across all stripes, and then a 2nd to 98th percentile peak-to-valley statistic. With the exposure time of each image and agitation state being the same, the CCD-noise is not expected to change much in between measurements, meaning that the rise in noise is directly tied to the fiber or more precisely to the agitation-state. The plot shows that noise is always higher in the static state. This is in agreement with results of prior works, that conclusively report mitigation of modal noise for agitated fibers (see e.g.: Petersburg et al. 2018; Oliva et al. 2019; Lemke et al. 2011).

Figure 9.1 (Right) shows the noise levels of each fiber in the agitated and static case. Now each bar represents the mean noise level of all five images, with errorbars displaying the standard deviation. This demonstrates that the qualitative results of Figure 9.1 (Left) are true across all fibers.

The results also seem relatively stable in comparison to each other for the same fiber state. Disregarding the 460B fiber for now, standard deviation for agitation is about 0.05 percentage points and for static about 0.2 at most. This shows that an agitated fiber has a much more stable noise level. The 460B fiber stands out in regards to deviation, since the noise is predominately created in the spectrograph-fiber and not the fiber under test. Since single-mode fibers can not have interacting modes, assuming they are used in the single-mode wavelength range, their far-field output is expected to be Gaussian. However, considering that the fiber is connected to the 33×132 spectrograph-fiber and therefore acts as a very small pinhole. This leads to the spectrograph fiber being severely underfilled and with that acting as the main source of noise in this configuration, with the 460B fiber.

The noise rises with shrinking fiber diameter, i.e. with a shrinking number of modes, as to be expected from modal noise. This is tied to the speckle-pattern of the fiber face. For smaller fibers and fewer modes, the speckle-pattern features less and larger spots, so the speckle-pattern grows more inhomogeneous. This in turn then creates larger differences in wavelength dependent loss and more noise.

To investigate how much of the noise is shot noise or read-out noise, we utilized another form

Figure 9.1: Bar plots showing noise levels for the static vs. agitated cases. Noise levels are in percent of the mean flux. Here, all images were taken with injection state "M" i.e. "Middle". **Left:** The 2nd to 98th percentile peak-to-valley noise of the 28E10 fiber. Each bar shows the values of one image in the series of the fiber. **Right:** The mean noise levels and standard deviation for all fibers in comparison. Mean and standard deviation are always calculated with respect to the five measurements for each fiber and state.

of analysis. This time each order will be evaluated independently, which gives additional information about potential wavelength dependence. In this case counts were low, with a maximum of about 2000. This of course boosts the impact of shot noise and potentially hides modal noise influence. The counts are better for measurements with a direct connection to the light source, which will be covered in coming sections.

The shot noise is most influential in orders that are within a minimum of the light sources spectrum, i.e. the area of 475nm and beyond 650nm.

Figure 9.2 shows two graphs displaying the evolution of the modeled noise, the fitted noise and the residual noise per-order for the 28E10 fiber. The x-axis indicates échelle orders, with 0 being the reddest and 50 the bluest. The overall structure displays the relative flux per order, where high values in noise represent low values in flux. The bump on the left is then explained by the lamps spectrum, which has a minimum in intensity around 475nm, and corresponds order 46 approximately.

It is clear that shot noise is dominant in the agitated case and mostly weak in comparison in the static case. Since the residual noise also scales with flux, as seen in the edge cases, this could indicate influence of noise other than modal noise. Nevertheless the lower data amounts in these areas could also lead to unexpected effects. To suppress these effects, we will concentrate interpretation on the well lit orders from 10 to 40.

Figure 9.3 shows the plots from before in the range of order 10 to 40 for all tested fibers. There is a clear general rise of total noise in the static case for every fiber. Shot noise is mostly constant across measurements, as is expected since there were no changes to light source or

Figure 9.2: Plots showing the noise per-order, for the 28E fiber. There are three types of noise shown: Total noise, the noise measured by fitting a Gaussian on the image’s flux histogram; Shot noise, the noise calculated with Equation 8.1 based on original flux; Residual noise, the noise calculated with Equation 8.2 based on total and shot noise. All values are based on all five measurements of each fiber state. X-axis shows order numbers from 0 to 50, from red to blue, so that on the left is the blue end and on the right the red end. **Left:** Fiber state static. **Right:** Fiber state agitated.

exposure time. The combined movement of the two noise levels leads to a change in residual noise. The differences of residual noise for static vs. agitated, appears to be more severe the smaller the fiber core diameter gets. Since these measurements are based on the same data as before, it is no surprise to see most severe noise with the single mode fiber. This is in agreement with Oliva et al. (2019), who have shown a significant increase in modal noise for underfilled fibers. The effects of under-illumination grow worse with decreasing fiber diameter.

In the case of every static fiber, there is a uptrend in residual noise towards the red end of the spectrum. This is an effect expected from modal noise, since the number of carrying modes decreases with wavelength, see Equations 2.9 and 2.10. In some cases, the same can be seen in the agitated case, albeit to a lesser extent.

Agitation significantly mitigates total noise for all fibers. When the test-fiber was agitated, the spectrograph fiber was still static and untouched. Since in this case, we are measuring the output of the spectrograph fiber, this shows that the effects of noise in the test-fiber still has a significant impact on the noise-properties of the connected fiber.

Figure 9.3: Plots showing the noise per-order for all fibers. Similar to Figure 9.2, but limited to orders 10-40. Fibers here are still indirectly coupled to the spectrograph. Agitated vs. Static fiber state are plotted next to each other for each fiber. Fiber diameter decreases for lower plots.

Figure 9.4: Plots showing the mean Fourier transform across all orders of each measurement, for the 28E fiber. Also for each measurement the initial slope is fitted with Equation 8.3.

Left: Fiber state static. **Right:** Fiber state agitated.

Fourier Analysis

An example of the initial FT with fit is shown in Figure 9.4. For this plot the first few datapoints are skipped, since these are dominated by background, blaze residues or other very large scale structures. The area interesting for modal noise is the linear down-slope in the left part of the graph. With rising Fourier frequencies the graph hits the noise floor. This part is dominated by shot noise. Figure 9.4 shows the FTs with fits for both fiber states. The larger the magnitude and the longer this magnitude is above the noise floor, the more severe the modal noise. Since the fit function (Equation 8.3) uses a as intercept and s as slope, one can interpret smaller a and larger s as indicators of better MN. Later in Figure 9.11 the parameters a and s are shown in a scatter plot for fiber and injection state for better comparison. Until then, concentrating on the effect of agitation, we can also see in Figure 9.5 that the low frequency noise is mitigated with agitation for every fiber type. Generally the trend seems to be a rise in s and decrease in a with agitation. There is no clear trend for severity of change between the two states but there is a trend regarding parameter a and the fiber core size. The bigger the core, the smaller a generally. This is in agreement with prior results, since lower a would mean less noise for larger core fibers.

In Figure 9.7 the results of the Fourier analysis are shown. Every line is the FT of their according order, with the bottom most line being the FT of échelle-order zero and as such the reddest. There is a clear structured part in the image of the 28E fiber. This was initially discovered after analyzing the time-series and is visible in most images in the coming chapters. The structures will be covered in a separate section (See Section 9.4) and will not be discussed here.

A commented exempt of the images is shown in Figure 9.6. There are visible bands at the edges. These are due to the lower fluxes at the ends of the spectrum and the therefore worse signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in these areas. Additionally to these shot noise bands, most of the images feature two distinct gradients. One towards lower and more red orders, which is expected from modal noise, since in the blue, more modes are excited and the speckle pattern becomes tighter, which leads to potential losses being minimized. The other horizontal gradient, towards lower frequencies, is something we have seen before in 9.4. As before we would associate a quicker,

Figure 9.5: Fit parameters for Fourier transform fits shown in Figure 9.4, for all fibers and states: Agitated and Static. Marker shape indicates Agitated vs. Static, filled vs. unfilled indicates Middle vs. Edge injection (here middle only), color indicates fiber.

Figure 9.6: Exempt of Figure 9.7 with comments. The red perimeter marks the shot noise bands, where flux in the original image is low enough for shot noise to dominate. There are two gradients, one of which is toward lower orders and implies more low-frequency noise for the redder orders. The other is toward lower frequencies, showing how the noise structure is made up of mainly low frequency modulations with a quick fall-off towards higher frequencies. This is similar to what can be seen in Figure 9.4.

Figure 9.7: Images of per-order Fourier transforms. Each line is the FT of the specified échelle-order in the original image. All images are cut-out to show the relevant low-frequency noise. Fiber core-size increases with lower images. Values are shown in log-scale, as indicated by the color-bar below.

Figure 9.8: Bar plot showing general noise levels for Static vs. Agitated fibers and light injection at the edge of the core. Similar to Figure 9.2, noise levels are peak-to-valley, 2nd to 98th percentile values and given in percent of mean flux.

weaker gradient or fall-off in horizontal direction with better modal noise.

In the right-side images of Figure 9.7 the shot noise bands are predominately visible on the far right, because the left range of the FT is dominated by MN. Similar to the plots in Figure 9.4 the fall-off of the magnitude is much steeper and starts out lower in the agitated case compared to the static case. Focusing on the right-side images again and disregarding the shot-noise bands, one can see how the fall-off is happening faster for higher and therefore bluer orders, creating the vertical gradient. Both the horizontal and vertical gradients are less dominant in the agitated images, due to mitigation of MN.

9.2 Illumination Changes

As mentioned before, we also tested how a change in the injection position affects the spectrum. The general expectation is that modal noise would increase, when injecting at the edge of the core. That is because modal noise decreases with the number of actively carrying modes, and central injection might hit more modes than an injection at the edge. The 460B single-mode fiber was not measured in this configuration, since the fiber is single-mode and differences in injection positions would only manifest in changes of flux.

Statistical Noise Analysis

The same measurements as in the section before were carried out with two injection positions: Middle and Edge. We have been looking at measurements from the middle position only for now. Figure 9.8 shows the general noise analysis for the edge injection position for every fiber. The general trend of agitation lowering the noise still holds, so does the trend of falling noise with increasing fiber diameter. These trends depend heavily on flux though. Since light injection at the edge results in more light lost at the fiber entrance, these results are biased towards worse overall noise because of increased shot noise.

The plots in Figure 9.9, provide a deeper understanding in this context. Here the shot noise is plotted together with the total noise and the residual noise, which is a more accurate tool for comparison between light injections. Generally one can see a overall higher noise level, as in the measurements for middle injection. For the 28E10 fiber the flux was approximately cut by half with edge injection, leading to an expected rise of shot noise by 40% in comparison to the same plot in Figure 9.3. This is of course reflected in the shot noise model, since it is calculated base on the flux.

Trends in Figure 9.9 are generally the same as for middle injection. Noise, total and residual, is higher for static fibers, and decreases with increasing fiber size. Also, there is again the trend of higher noise for increasing wavelength.

Fourier Analysis

The same kind of Fourier analysis was done as in the section before. Figure 9.10 shows examples of the fit to the FTs.

Again the same trends show, the initial fall-off is steeper for agitation. To compare this with the other injection method, the fit parameters have been plotted in Figure 9.11. Here for each fiber, except the 460B, there are four species: Middle Agitated, Middle Static, Edge Agitated, and Edge Static. Clearly the agitated values are segregated from the static ones, while agitated fibers show generally higher values in s and lower values in a as their static counter part.

There also are some trends regarding core size. Roughly one can see, that lower core sizes seem to be correlated with lower a values. This is only broken by the M64 and 28E fibers, which have core sizes of $10\mu\text{m}$ and $8.2\mu\text{m}$ respectively. This trend is more clear in the static measurements, which may be more reliable for detecting differences in the fibers themselves. For agitated measurements, slight differences in how the agitation is set up can alter the values when comparing fibers.

The per-order type of Fourier Analysis, is shown in Figure 9.12. For all fibers, there is a clear difference for static vs. agitated. In all static cases, there is significantly more low-frequency noise. Again with a fall-off that extends more into higher frequencies for lower and therefore more red échelle-orders. The differences between the static fibers are slight. There is less of a gradient in y - or order-direction for larger-core fibers, then the few-mode fibers. Meanwhile the gradient towards lower frequency noise stays mostly constant. For the agitated fibers there are barely any significant differences in the per-order Fourier transforms. All exhibit the same shot noise dominated bands at the top and bottom.

All together the features of the per-order FTs are similar to the ones in Figure 9.7. The only minor difference would be that the gradient in y -direction appears to be more dominant for middle injection, then for injection at the edge. This is true for both the agitated and static case for some fibers.

Figure 9.9: Plots showing the noise per-order for all fibers. Same as Figure 9.3, but for edge injection. The plots show a higher overall noise level, compared to static fibers with the same injection state. Noise levels increase again for decreasing fiber diameter and show trend of higher noise levels in the red. Compared to middle injection, noise is slightly higher for few-mode fibers and mostly the same for multimode fibers.

Figure 9.10: Plots showing the mean Fourier transform across all orders of each measurement, for the 28E fiber and edge-case light injection. Also for each measurement the initial slope is fitted with Equation 8.3. **Left:** Fiber state: Static. **Right:** Fiber state: Agitated.

Figure 9.11: Plot for fit parameters of Fourier transform fits. Same as Figure 9.5, but augmented with Edge measurements. Marker shape indicates Agitated vs. Static, filled vs. unfilled indicates Middle vs. Edge injection, color indicates fiber.

Figure 9.12: Images of per-order Fourier transforms, similar to Figure 9.7, for Edge injection. Each line is the FT of the specified échelle-order in the original image. All images are cut-out to show the relevant low-frequency noise. Fiber core-size increases with lower images. Values are shown in log-scale, as indicated by the color-bar below.

Figure 9.13: Images of the normalized, collapsed stripes of the three fibers used in indirect, time-series configuration. Each line in these images corresponds to one échelle-order. These are each one example of the images captured in the time-series. All images are divided by their respective mean-image over the time-axis.

9.3 Time Series

The time series results will be split in the categories of direct and indirect coupling. As mentioned before, the initial time-series measurements were carried out with an additional fiber between the fiber under test and the spectrograph, which may alter results quantitatively but not necessarily qualitatively. From now on all measurements are carried out with static fibers and overfilled central illumination.

9.3.1 Indirect Coupling

The most general and intuitive way of visualizing change in the spectrum, would be to make a video from the 60 or so images taken. Since this is not a great visualization on paper, Figure 9.13 shows only some impressions of that. As described in Section 8.4, the orders are extracted in both wide and single line format, then normalized.

Here we can already see some recurring features. There are again shot-noise dominated bands at the highest and lowest orders, best visible for the C100 fiber. The flux for each of the measurements was kept around 40.000 in the brightest orders. It is only due to other noise factors

gaining in severity, that the shot-noise bands are suppressed for the smaller core fibers. This can be gathered by looking at the values on the color bar. Shot-noise is expected to stay the same for the same flux, but the boundaries of the color bars, which are set to 0.5% and 99.5% of the flux distribution, broaden with decreasing fiber core diameter.

This already roughly shows the dependence of MN on the core diameter. But since MN is wavelength dependent, we want to restrict the analysis of noise values to smaller wavelength bands. The before mentioned SOTS images (see Section 8.4.1) work better for this purpose, and show change within one order of the spectrum, see Figure 9.14. Here we have a small cutout of the time evolution of order 26. Every line of this image is the same order at different points in time over a range of 60 minutes, with 60 images total, so one image per minute (except for the 28E measurement, where it was 40 minutes and 40 images). Every line was divided by the mean over time for normalization. This means that differences in value of 0.01 correspond to 1% in flux. The wavelength range this cutout corresponds to, is about 5698 to 5710Å and was kept the same for each fiber.

It is clear that the noise structures are highly variable and mostly random in this case. Comparing this image to the same range for other fibers, as in Figure 9.14, we do not see much change in size or frequency of the noise structure. The only clearly changing parameter is the range of flux-value. In the three examples with the C100 multimode, 28E few-mode and the 460B single-mode fibers the ranges change from about 2%, to 10%, to 25% in the 99.5% range of each dataset, respectively. This is expected behavior by now in the case for indirect coupling. We have already established that, since the single mode fiber acts as a very small pinhole for the fiber that is connected to the spectrograph, we achieve what is basically a worst case scenario when it comes to modal noise. Also the noise levels again decrease with fiber size.

As mentioned before, we also extract the orders in a "wide"-format, meaning each order is not collapsed to a single line, but as a few-pixel wide cut-out of each order. They then are straightened and extracted as those few-pixel wide lines. This preserves spatial structures in cross-dispersion direction of the échelle-spectrum and hence it preserves spatial structures over the fiber face in the same direction. Figure 9.15 shows some examples of this in SOTS format. Again, each image shows the same order evolving in time. Clearly there are plenty of repeating structures, but most slightly change with time. Comparing the different fibers, there does not seem to be a difference to the pace of change or to the amount of structures. The differences of the peak-to-peak values of the changing structures resemble the values from before. Although these images are much more noisy, since the wide stripes pick up a lot of low flux pixels towards the outer rims of each order.

Figure 9.14: Single-order time-series (SOTS) images of the three fibers used in indirect time-series configuration. Each image shows échelle-order 26. Each line is the same échelle-order from a different image in the time-series, each spaced one minute apart.

Figure 9.15: Wide single-order time-series (SOTS) images of the three fibers used in indirect time-series configuration. Each image shows échelle-order 26. Each six lines are the same échelle-order from a different image in the time-series, spaced one minute apart. These wide stripes are plotted, how they appear on the CCD, just straightened and cut to six pixel wide lines. Underlying images are the same as for Figure 9.14.

Figure 9.16: Noise per-order for all fibers in time-series, indirect coupling configuration. All measured orders included.

Statistical Noise Analysis

Figure 9.16 shows the same type of analysis that has been done before for agitation and light injection tests, for all fibers tested in this configuration. This time all orders are included, since the SNR, with the higher general flux in this measurement, is higher and shot noise is less dominant. This is not quite true for the C100 fiber. The residual noise here is low enough for shot noise to have a significant impact.

Since these plots are based on the SOTS images from before, the differences in noise severity between fibers are the same. The higher flux is reflected in the plots with shot noise levels around 0.2%. In the case of the single-mode and few-mode fibers, the residual noise clearly makes up most of the measured noise. For the multimode fiber the residual noise part is suppressed so much that residual levels are only about three times as high at most. In all residual noise dominated areas, there is a clear increase of the residual noise component with decreasing order, i.e. with increasing wavelength.

Fourier Analysis

Figure 9.17 shows the Fourier analysis of the same principle as in Figure 9.7 or 9.12 from before. Generally the plots look much smoother. This is because instead of being based on five measurements as before, now these plots are a mean-combination of 60 images, with much

higher SNR each. As expected, all images show an extended tail of noise towards the lower, redder orders. The gradient is now much better visible than before. For the C100 fiber the tails fall off much quicker than for the others. Additionally the Fourier magnitudes are much lower than in the other plots, as indicated by the values on the color bar. This also explains why only here the shot noise bands are visible. The MN and shot noise levels are similar enough for them to both show up in this plot. This is in agreement with the statistical noise analysis from before.

9.3.2 Direct Coupling

When coupling directly, the size of the fiber core also influences the width of the orders in the échelle. Figure 9.18 shows a part of the raw échelle spectrum for the C100 and the single mode 460B. Clearly the stripes of the C100 are much wider, warranting having a look at the wide-format. On the contrary, it is expected that the wide-format for the 460B and similarly sized fibers will not provide additional information, since their stripes are just about one pixel wide.

Because flux is summed over the cross-dispersion direction and stripes are now generally smaller than before, flux values will also be smaller. This results in higher, but still manageable shot noise values.

Figure 9.19 shows an example of a wide SOTS image for fiber C100 in both direct and indirect coupling. There still clearly is some large scale structure, slowly changing in time when coupling directly. The scale of the structures seems to be larger in direct coupling, that is in wavelength direction. Strictly looking at the height of the structures in y - or time-direction, they seem more or less similar, there are just fewer patches.

In Figure 9.20 are some examples for SOTS images in the non-wide format. The cut-out is over the same wavelength range as in every SOTS image before. The changing pattern across all fibers seems to be much more orderly. The single-mode fiber exhibits no structural patterns at all and seems to be reduced to shot noise. All the other fibers have structures of vastly differing size and apparent pace of change. The C100 seems to be the only one exhibiting multiple peak-to-peak rotations across the full timescale of the time-series. Peak-to-peak values are below 1% for the C100, C18 and 460B, for the remaining two few-mode fibers peak-to-peak values are around 8%. The structure visible in each image is unstable across orders. Appendix A exhibits some examples of the visible structures and patterns for the 28E10 fiber across multiple orders and full examples of the other fibers. There seems to be no clear dependency of noise pattern with wavelength in either pace of change or size.

Figure 9.17: Per-order Fourier transforms of the noise in the fibers measured in indirect time-series configuration. Each line corresponds to one order, at the bottom is the red-, and at the top is the blue-end.

Figure 9.18: Cutout of the raw images for direct coupling. **Left:** Single-mode fiber, 460B. **Right:** Multimode fiber, C100.

Figure 9.19: Cutout of the single-order time-series images in wide-format, for the C100 in direct and indirect coupling.

Figure 9.20: Single-order time-series images for every fiber with direct coupling. Example images of order 26, and cut-outs. X-axis represents pixels in dispersion direction and wavelength as indicated by the above axis. Y-axis represents image number of the time-series and passed time in minutes.

Statistical Noise Analysis

Figure 9.21 shows the noise analysis per-order for each fiber. The process is the same as before. As expected, residual noise is highest with the few-mode fibers and mitigated for multimode as well as for single-mode. The 460B single-mode fiber does not have zero residual noise, even in direct coupling, indicating influence of another non-modal noise source. This is not unexpected, but with the noise being well within 0.0025% in standard deviation, its influence should be insignificant to our cause.

The few-mode fibers are very prominent. Their noise is quite unstable in between orders, indicating that raw modal noise might be very dynamic. Additionally they are the only ones, where residual noise dominates. There is no visible wavelength dependency, contrary to what was the case before. This might be because of the high dynamic range of modal noise in this direct configuration. There is no clear core size dependency, the two multimode fibers have residual noise levels almost as low as the single mode fiber. This is the case despite the fact, that there is still clear structure in the single-order time-series images of Figure 9.20, implying that structure in the SOTS images might be a more precise tool for judging noise.

Fourier Analysis

The Fourier analysis for this dataset is quite eventful. Figure 9.22 displays the FTs in the already discussed style for every fiber. Starting with the most boring, the 460B fiber only displays shot noise, no fading and no structure, as is expected. The C100 is similar to the single-mode one, except for one singular vertical stripe, indicating some large scale structure mostly independent of order. Only the width changes with order, getting wider in the red, which is similar behavior to what we have seen before.

All other fibers exhibit highly structured noise patterns of differing severity. These structures will be discussed in more detail in the following section. Apart from the obvious pattern, there seems only to be the shot noise at the edges visible as seen in the other images. There is no indication of any gradients as we exhibited for indirect coupling. This might be due to suppression by the more prevalent structures.

Figure 9.21: Per-order noise analysis for all fiber in direct connection configuration.

Figure 9.22: Per-order Fourier transforms for all fibers, when directly connected to the spectrograph. Every line is the FT of one order, with blue at the top and red at the bottom.

9.4 Fourier Signatures of Fiber Modes

The structures seen in the FTs before, most prominently in Figure 9.22, are likely connected to the modal effects of the tested fibers. Their severity is correlated to the number of modes carrying light, and their structure suggests underlying wavelength dependency. The 28E fiber in Figure 9.22 is structurally most interesting. There seem to be multiple orders of structures present, perhaps corresponding to modes being cut-off at certain wavelengths.

Structures are mitigated more for fibers with larger diameter, as seen in for the other fiber in the same Figure, and do not show up for single-mode fibers.

There also is slight structure in the FT of the indirect fiber measurements, as seen in Figure 9.17. This is interesting, because the fiber carrying light from the test-fiber to the spectrograph is multimode, and generally should not exhibit properties close to the 28E fiber in the FT. This hints towards, that these patterns might be created at the fiber interface in a similar way as in the spectrograph or that the modal properties of the 28E fiber are propagated through the spectrograph fiber to create such patterns. In any case the effect is evidently not as strong as when connecting the fiber directly.

The same Figure, also shows that there are no patterns in the FT of the 460B Single-Mode fiber, affirming that the patterns are not solely caused by underfilling the spectrograph fiber, or the spectrograph fiber itself in another way. The C100 fiber in the same Figure also does not exhibit structures either. The underlying raw structure of the C100 is less distinct than that of the 28E. This results in a recreation of the effect as before, but is too weak to be detected here.

The same can be said, when looking at the the images in Figure 9.7, where fibers were also connected indirectly. Here too the 28E is the only fiber exhibiting structure. Additionally one can see that agitation does not seem to have an effect on the structure.

Figure 9.12 is the only per-order Fourier analysis without any visible structure. In this case the fibers were illuminated at the edge. This may suggest, that the central modes are most relevant for the structure we see.

10 Conclusion

We found strong differences in the manifestation of Modal Noise between multi-, few- and single-mode fibers. Few-mode fibers exhibit by far the most severe MN, multi-mode fibers, on the other hand, prove relatively stable in comparison, while single-mode fibers perform best, as is expected. Agitation positively affects MN, mitigating the effects but not completely removing them. Fourier analysis reveals characteristic spatial and therefore spectral frequency modulations, manifesting as structural pattern in the Fourier-transformed spectrum. The MN effects of fibers are distinguished in magnitude, wavelength-dependence and temporal behavior.

Our approach for the measurements with a actively used, high-resolution fiber-fed échelle spectrograph, provides a realistic footprint and cut-off geometry. This ensures valid data accumulation under realistic conditions. The multi-method analysis based on statistics, time-series, histograms and Fourier transforms, help to get a complete picture on how MN manifests itself. Testing multiple fibers with different properties highlights dependencies on fiber type. On the other hand are the results limited by the usage of improvised poorly controlled agitation, leaving influence of frequency or amplitude of the agitation unclear.

The results of our measurements can be related to known MN theory. Differences in magnitude and wavelength-dependence are caused by speckle behavior. Few-mode fibers exhibit higher contrast and fewer speckles due to stronger interference of the limited number of modes. Since speckle patterns change with wavelength, these changes are more severe for a more inhomogeneous beam with fewer speckles. If clipping at one or multiple spectrograph components occur, there will be differences of throughput depending on whether more or less speckles are in the clipped beam part. This creates wavelength dependent throughput changes, resulting in MN. Multi-mode fibers, which have a much higher number of speckles, have more homogeneous far-fields. When the speckle pattern changes due to wavelength, the resulting variations of the spectral power-distribution are not as strong. This plausibly explains the more controlled MN behavior of multi-mode fibers. Here the speckle pattern is more intricate and has less contrast. The far-field becomes more stable and more uniform, not removing MN on the spectrum but making it more stable. In the case of single-mode fibers, their output beam is a completely uniform Gaussian. There are no multiple modes that could be interfering with each other, resulting in the absence of a speckle pattern, removing MN completely.

Mechanical movement of the fiber affects the speckle pattern, changing how the modes interfere and moving the speckle positions in the near- and far-field. Frequent agitation therefore leads to an averaging of the speckles over time and with exposure times larger then the timescale of the agitation period, that results in mitigation of modal noise, as seen in the measurements. Clearly frequency and amplitude of the agitation affect its efficiency, but with the improvised device these parameter could not be varied for our measurements.

As would be expected, the pure magnitude of MN changes slightly with wavelength. The number of modes decreases with increase of wavelength squared, leading to the speckles becoming fewer in number and higher in contrast over the wavelength range of 450-750nm, worsening MN in the red. This leads in most cases to significantly lower noise-floors in the bluest compared to the reddest order. This can be seen in most per-order noise analysis plots, and is suppressed by agitation. When measuring MN in direct connection, this trend disappears partly due to severe instabilities in the noise for few-mode fibers. The other fibers are much more stable in comparison. This shows the unstable nature of MN when measured directly in a worst case scenario. Just by employing a fiber with eight microns more in core diameter, not only lowers the MN to a fraction of the intensity but also suppresses variations significantly.

Temporal instabilities of MN become apparent on time scales of an hour. Plausibly these are the same timescales as those on which the speckle patterns vary. In this case, the variations are independent of the wavelength-dependent variations that create MN in the first place. Temporal variations might be caused by thermal instability, mechanical instability or vibrations of the spectrograph components or the fiber. The Waltz spectrograph is set in its own room, but is not thermally controlled. It is unclear if it is mainly the speckle pattern that causes variations or if spectrograph components themselves induce throughput or cut-off variations, therefore changing how MN affects the spectrum over time. Very long exposure images could then show reduction of MN since effects on large timescales noise could be averaged out. This is not practical though since typically high-resolution spectrograph would be in highly controlled environments, and therefore natural temporal instabilities would be likely reduced. Agitation of course would be an example of a deliberately induce mechanical instability on low time scales, affecting MN positively.

Modal noise typically appears in the lower-frequency regions of Fourier transforms and decreases in strength as the frequency increases. On higher frequencies the noise-floor, consisting predominately of shot-noise, dominates. When measured indirectly, MN manifests as gradients toward lower frequencies and redder orders. As already mentioned, redder orders are expected to have worse MN because of a lower active mode number. Orders with worse MN then exhibit higher Fourier amplitude and a slower fall-off towards higher frequencies. This means the higher frequency components of the noise are more pronounced, which is likely caused by the more sensitive speckle pattern and a more sensitive reaction to slighter changes of wavelength. Another factor in this configuration is that the FSR of the spectrograph increases toward longer wavelengths, causing redder échelle orders to include a wider wavelength range. It is not clear how exactly the speckle pattern behaves for slight changes of wavelength, but it is clear that there are more speckles with shorter wavelengths. This means that the pattern must change and move when advancing in wavelength. These movements likely cause modal noise by clipping and creating wavelength-dependent variations in throughput and therefore an unstable spectral power-distribution. Given that the redder orders include a wider wavelength range or FSR, the Fourier transforms of red orders include a wider range of speckle movements. If the

speckle movement accelerates with increasing wavelength, the frequency of throughput variations would change, ultimately leading to a higher spatial frequency of MN on the detector, which then could cause the gradients in the Fourier transform. To confirm this though, one would need a deeper understanding of how the speckle patterns change with small wavelength adjustments.

The Fourier signatures are most visible when the fibers are directly connected to the spectrograph. They clearly change with the number of modes in the tested fiber. Their apparent severity, intricacy or strength seem to scale similarly to MN itself. Few-mode fibers show the most pronounced structures, while for multi-mode fibers the structures seem weaker or heavily constrained to very low frequencies, in case of the 100 μ m-core fiber. With the exception of the low-frequency stripe the Fourier transform of the largest fiber resembles that of the single-mode fiber, paralleling the characteristics of general MN amplitude. This suggests that these structures are formed by the interaction of modes through a complex mechanism based on the geometry and interactions of the spectrograph components. If further investigated these structures could help to gain more insight into the exact mechanisms of MN creation and could perhaps even be used to directly characterize a fibers modal properties by the structure alone.

We tested the fibers with the MN implications for ANDES-K in mind. Measurements were done in the visual, while ANDES-K will operate in the K-band. To ensure the measurements are still relevant, the fibers were chosen so that the number of modes is to scale with the number of modes the actually planned fibers would be operating with.

The few-mode fibers introduce a strong source of noise, that can be suppressed by agitation, but hardly removed. Because of its not-static nature, the MN cannot be reduced by flat-fielding. As previously mentioned MN ultimately leads to variations in the power distribution of the spectrum. These wavelength-dependent spectral power variations lead to slight shifts of the spectral-line centroids, which then affects RV and other high-accuracy wavelength measurements. For ANDES-K specifically, using few-mode fibers might endanger the high-resolution goals if no advanced agitation devices are used. Considering limited space and higher material wear, using single-mode fibers with a throughput trade-off might be warranted.

We propose a follow-up simulation of how realistic wavelength-dependent speckle patterns could lead to structured MN. To ensure a realistic basis, it would be useful to first study the exact dependency of speckle patterns to small wavelength variations. At the same time it would prove useful for the understanding of temporal MN instabilities, to study the variations of speckle patterns with temperature, mechanical stress or vibrations. MN Simulations could be done by using the `pyEchelle`¹ package with a custom speckle pattern input based on previous measurements. This could be used to replicate the patterns, structures and amplitudes that we measured, providing insight to the mechanisms leading to MN. In the same way one could study the influence of several factors, as e.g. how cut-off at certain components affects MN and

¹<https://gitlab.com/Stuermer/pyechelle>

if it disappears if an instrument without beam-clipping is simulated. Realistic MN simulations then could show the exact influence that MN has on real-world measurements like RV. This would paint a clear picture of MN as a source of error in any applicable situation.

To improve on the current set-up, one could switch to a light source with more evenly distributed power. This would get rid of the low power bump at around 475\AA and increase the amount and quality of usable data. Also one could concentrate on more few-mode fibers, since these exhibit the most pronounced modal noise effects. It would also be interesting to test MN with other core geometries and input conditions, e.g. different F-ratios. One could also try to limit the excited number of modes further by applying a smaller pinhole, that way one could also try to select a small subset of modes to see how that affects the spectrum and the Fourier signatures.

Another improvement could be made to the agitation device, since the improvised machine, while still significantly improving MN, is bound to have a limited effect when compared to more elaborate machines. Testing different agitation devices frequencies and amplitudes, while comparing their effects in this configuration could lead to clearer differences and improve the understanding of mitigation by agitation.

Our findings highlight the impact of modal noise on spectra, and therefore on high precision spectroscopy. We emphasize the complexity of the mechanism leading to structured modal noise, and how its understanding could provide a solid basis for further improving the precision of fiber-fed instruments.

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Appendix A: List of items used in the setup

Item	Designation
Light sources	Main: Leukos Samba-W Auxiliary: Thorlabs white mounted LED: Type MWWHL4 with LEDD1B driver
Filter Wheels	Color: Thorlabs ELLA2 Filter Wheel Adapter, Mounted ELL18/M Rotation Stage F-ratios: QHYCCD, QHYCFW3, Motor Driver Color Filter Wheel
Pinholes	Thorlabs P5HK, P10HK, P25HK, P40HK
Photodiodes	Thorlabs S120C (2)
Powermeter	Thorlabs PM320E
Cameras	Near-Field: Thorlabs DCC1545M-GL (2) Far-Field: QHY600PH
Optical Components	Lenses: TRH254-040-A-ML (2), TTL200-S8 Objectives: Mitutoyo 10x OAPs: MPD249-G01 (2) Beamsplitters: CM1-BP150 (2)
Linear motor	PI M-228, with C-663 Stepper Motor Controller

Appendix B: Fiber Datasheet Example

Fiber Datasheet for: R_25x40_0000_0001

Fiber Data

Name	R_25x40_0000_0001
Dimensions [μm]	['25', '40']
Shape	rectangular
Length [m]	4
Numerical Aperture	0.22
Coating Type	Acrylate
Manufacturer	

Fiber End Faces

FRD Results

Farfield of the fiber with virtual apertures

Input f/6.21 with artificial apertures

Horizontal Farfield Cut

Scrambling Gain Results

Minimum Scrambling Gain: $SG_{min} = 297$

Horizontal Nearfield Cut

Behavior for different input spot positions

Far-field behavior for different input spot positions

Entrance

Exit

Entrance

Exit

Appendix C: Single-order time-steps, impressions

Figure C.1: Full single-order time-steps for every fiber used in direct configuration. Each image displaying order 26.

Figure C.2: Full single-order time-steps for fiber 28E. Differing échelle-orders.

Erklärung

Ich versichere, dass ich diese Arbeit selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt habe.

Heidelberg, den 28.11.2025,

Vincent Benz